
TEACHERS' EXPERIENCES LIVING IN THE INDIGENOUS PEOPLES (IP) COMMUNITY: BASIS FOR POLICY RECOMMENDATION

Eva Mae D. Geneta, LPT

Certified Teacher

American Horse School

Pass Creek District, South Dakota, USA

Abstract

This qualitative study aimed to determine the teachers' experiences living in the indigenous people's community during the COVID-19 pandemic for Academic Year 2021-2022. The research method utilized in the study was qualitative using in-depth interview and the design was ethnography. The research instrument utilized in this study was a researcher-made interview schedule. Audio and video recorders were also used for data gathering and documentation. Thematic approach was used to analyze the data gathered. It was found out that the teachers encountered varied experiences classified as difficulty in workplace, safety and security, learners' habitual behavior, DDU (depressed, dilapidated, & underserved) school, far from the town and difficult roads, poor learners' achievement, teaching the basic literacy, learning modality as a challenge, observing health protocols, culture shock, good communication with the community of non-IP teachers, adjustment of married teachers, giving extrinsic motivation, complex work arrangement during pandemic, exhaustion, and support from external stakeholders.

Keywords: Experiences, IP Community, Living, Teachers, Policy Recommendation

Chapter 1 Introduction

Background of the Study

Teaching is a multifaceted profession where teachers are required to perform a lot of duties expected of them, accomplish obligations adhering to their mandate, and carry out abrupt demands of work. These demands may or may not be compensated, hence making teaching a stressful profession.

In accordance with Sections 3 and 4 of RA No. 7836 (the Philippine Teachers Professionalization Act of 1994), which is referenced in the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers of the Philippines (Resolution No. 435, 1997), it is emphasized that "every teacher shall be physically, mentally, and morally fit. Every teacher shall possess and actualize a full communicative capacity."

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VI (June 2024), p.57-103, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

However, teachers are just mere human beings with individual differences who also face struggles, shortcomings, difficulties, and challenges. One of the challenges faced by the teachers in these difficult times is the teaching-learning delivery amidst the COVID-19 pandemic.

The COVID-19 epidemic disrupted education to the greatest extent ever because it affected students and instructors almost everywhere in the world (United Nations, 2020). Despite the COVID-19 pandemic, teachers have consistently been ranked among the most stressful professions due to a variety of factors, including heavy workloads, excessive administrative responsibilities, strained relationships with coworkers and school leaders, and challenging work-life balance, according to Johnson et al. (2005), as stated in Mari et al. (2021).

According to Barro, et al. (2021), the pandemic has changed how teachers allocate their time between teaching, interacting with students, and administrative responsibilities.

According to the Department of Education (2020), during the the first South East Asian Ministers of Education Organization (SEAMEO) Ministerial Policy e-Forum, Dr. Leonor M. Briones stated that the first principle that the department adhered to and to which it is committed, in compliance with the Preseident's directive, is to ensure that learning continues in the midst of the pandemic; however, the safety, health and well-being of learners, teachers, and personnel should be protected and safeguarded to prevent the further transmission of the disease.

DepEd responded to the problem of developing innovative educational delivery mechanisms in schools by introducing the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP). Through the BE-LCP, learners across the nation had options for the learning modality that was most appropriate for their circumstances.

Due to the shift to new learning modalities mandated by the pandemic, it is challenging for those teachers in the Schools District of Calinog II assigned in the Indigenous People (IP) communities to grasp distance teaching and remote learning. The IP communities' highlands, distant barangays, and hard-to-reach areas are where these schools are situated. It is crucial to comprehend how teachers in the Indigenous People (IP) community develop over time at managing the regular demands and difficulties associated with the teaching profession in order to prevent burnout in teachers as well as to encourage their engagement, learning, mastery, and efficiency.

With this, the sources of teachers' stress have multiplied with the advent of COVID-19.

Thus, the study shifted its focus to detailing the teachers' experiences living in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) community for the School Year 2021–2022 in times of COVID-19 pandemic or the "new normal" in order to contribute to the expanding literature on the effects of the pandemic on educators.

Statement of the Problem

The study was conducted to describe the experiences of teachers who are teaching in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) community for School Year 2021-2022.

Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of teacher-respondents in terms of age, sex, position, length of service, marital status, & ethnicity?
2. What are the experiences of teachers who are living in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) community?
3. What policy can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

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National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Significance of the Study

The results of the study may be significant and may be beneficial to the following groups in the educational system:

Teachers. The study's findings may inform and enlighten teachers, who can then focus efforts on professional development in regards to giving feedback on coping techniques. As educators, they might also be able to handle difficulties in life without having a negative impact on their social, emotional, physical, or mental well-being.

Indigenous Peoples (IP) Community. The results of this study may let the IP community realize the importance of teachers. They may appreciate the guidance and dedication offered by the teachers to give IP learners the education they deserve. The IP Community could further give their cooperation to teachers in terms of building their community into a better place for all inhabitants and helping them become responsible citizens as well.

Learners. The research findings may let learners be aware of teachers' experiences and coping mechanisms in providing them quality education amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. Understanding, concern, and faith can be developed among learners knowing that they are well supported at school, especially by the teachers.

School Heads. The research findings may motivate school heads to plan or conduct in-service training and implement faculty development with an emphasis on protocols and strategies in teaching within the Indigenous Peoples (IP) communities. This may give them a better understanding of the importance of teachers' experience and coping mechanisms in learners' education. They could use this to utilize their authority as head of the school to address difficulties in teaching and learning in the IP communities when faced with sudden situations in times of pandemic.

Department of Education (DepEd). The findings of the study may be helpful in developing programs to support teacher wellbeing. The results would be used as the foundation for developing activities that might aid teachers in strengthening their coping mechanisms, reducing stress, and advising them on how to manage stress brought on by the demands of their jobs. Additionally, this will aid DepEd employees in understanding the efforts made by teachers in IP communities during the pandemic crisis.

External Stakeholders. The research findings may further provide information to external stakeholders, regarding teachers' experiences and coping mechanisms in times of pandemic, thus, will make them further realize the importance of quality education in IP communities. It will fervently motivate them in giving full support to the needs of the teachers & learners and seamless cooperation to DepEd's activities and programs.

Policy Makers. The inputs generated would be beneficial to educational planners in improving the IP curriculum and strategizing programs that focus on the needs and well-being of teachers teaching in the Indigenous Peoples community.

Future Researchers. The study could further help future researchers because there is a lack of research regarding teachers' work-related experience and coping mechanisms in the Indigenous People (IP) communities. Future researches could explore additional conditions associated with the adoption of specific coping mechanisms and the experiences of the teachers. They may benefit from the findings of this study as they may be provided baseline information for conducting related studies.

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National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The study aimed to describe the experiences of teachers who are teaching in the Indigenous People (IP) community during the COVID-19 pandemic for School Year 2021-2022.

The study used descriptive method using in-depth interview. The interviewer during the interview was allowed to sit and to think about the series of questions about a certain issue. The aim was to get the main or the necessary views of the participants in a certain issue in a social context through the responses of the participants to the questions.

The study employed qualitative research design using ethnography. Ethnography refers to both the data gathering of anthropology and the development of analysis of specific peoples, settings, or ways of life. Edith Cowan University (December 2021)

The participants of the study were the twelve (12) purposely chosen teachers in the Schools District of Calinog II, who are living in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) community during School Year 2021-2022. The participants were selected using convenient and purposeful sampling approaches. They were chosen based on their capacity to provide the required data as well as taking into account their availability at the time of data collection. Although this sample does not accurately reflect all teachers, it is deemed sufficient to illustrate the study's qualitative goal.

The research instruments utilized in the study were researcher-made interview schedule, voice, and video recorder. The instrument passed through the content validity test by the panel of experts to ensure intelligibility, appropriateness, and relevance. Corrections, comments, and suggestions of the validators and panel were considered and applied.

In the study, in-depth interview under the qualitative research design was utilized through audio and video recording following the minimum health protocol standards required by the Inter Agency Task Force (IATF), Local Government Unit (LGU) of the Municipality of Calinog, and the Department of Education (DepEd).

The interviewer during the interview was allowed to sit and to ask series of questions pertaining to certain issues. The aim was to get the main idea or the necessary views of the participants in a certain issue in a social context through the responses of the participants to the questions (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2007).

Thematic approach was used to analyze the data gathered from the interview.

Definition of Terms

For clarity and understanding of the important terms used in the study, the following terms were conceptually and operationally defined.

Basis. The bottom of something considered as its foundation or the principal component of something (Merriam-Webster Dictionary, 2022).

In the study, the term referred to the foundation or the underpinning element.

Experiences. The process of doing and seeing things and of having things happen to you, the skill or knowledge that you get by doing, & the length of time that you have spent doing something (e.g. such as a particular job) (Merriam-Webster Dictionary, 2022).

In the study, the term referred to the things seen & happened to the teacher, the skills & knowledge that the teacher gets while he/she is assigned in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) community during the COVID-19 pandemic

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Indigenous Cultural Communities/Indigenous Peoples. ICCs/IPs are homogenous societies identified by self-ascription and ascription, who have lived on communally bounded and defined territory since time immemorial, sharing common bonds of language, customs, traditions, and other distinctive cultural traits (Republic Act No. 8371).

In the study, the term referred to remote or far-flung communities in Calinog, Iloilo inhabited or populated predominantly by Indigenous People.

Living. Having life or exhibiting the life or motion of nature (Merriam-Webster Dictionary, 2022).

In the study, the term referred to the function or action, work, and existence of teachers in the IP community.

Policy Recommendation. It is a written policy advice prepared for some group or person that has the authority to make or to influence policy decisions, serves to inform people who are faced with policy choices on particular issues about how research and evidence can help to make the best decisions. It is about using research to solve a public policy problem or to provide evidence about how a policy is working (CARDI, n.d.).

In the study, the phrase referred to the management of processes or a specific course of action chosen from among alternatives in light of the circumstances at hand to direct and affect decisions made in the present and the future toward something that is proposed as right or advantageous.

Teacher/s. It is a person or thing that teaches or a person whose job is to teach students about certain subjects (Merriam-Webster Dictionary, 2022).

In the study, the term referred to a person or persons that teaches or is assigned in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) communities in the Schools District of Calinog II in the Municipality of Calinog.

Chapter 2

Review of Related Literature and Studies

This chapter discusses conceptual literatures and research studies relevant at investigating teachers' experiences in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) community during the COVID-19 pandemic for School Year 2021-2022, in order to present background information, which would support the conduct of this investigation. It is divided into three parts: (1) impact of pandemic on education in the indigenous peoples (IP) Community, (2) teachers' experiences during pandemic, (3) teachers' coping mechanism, (4) the theoretical and conceptual frameworks, and (5) schematic diagram of the study.

Impact of Pandemic on Education in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) Community

Native American boys, girls, and teenagers have been more adversely impacted in Latin America by the unexpected and required school closures brought on by the pandemic. Most nations participating in COVID-19 have chosen different types of remote learning that use the Internet, television, or radio. The absence of reliable electricity or Internet access, as well as the lack of distance learning equipment in families, may make it difficult for rural residents to access education (UNICEF, n.d.).

According to TEBTEBBA (2020), participants who are indigenous and live in remote areas in the south of the Philippines must hire a habal-habal (hire motorcycle), which costs

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VI (June 2024), p.57-103, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

about 600 PHP (12.40 USD) per trip. It also takes around half a day to travel to the spot with the closest internet coverage.

The COVID-19 epidemic has made it evident that educational measures are biased against monolingual Spanish-speaking students, whether intentionally or not, with little content generated in indigenous languages, according to the study done by Sánchez-Cruz et al. (2021). This reinforces the propensity to overlook or dismiss minority languages in favor of dominant ones, like Spanish. The constitutional right of indigenous peoples to high-quality education is thus seriously jeopardized in the wake of the COVID-19 health catastrophe.

The IPs must be able to value education in accordance with their own values, and they must also see the value of education, the necessity for a system that can be utilized to spread education throughout their communities, and then take ownership of that system. To truly comprehend how the system may assist them advance their lives and strengthen their culture, they must take ownership of it for themselves. The IPs must be encouraged to become self-reliant in order to meet the challenges posed by changes in their own culture, communities, and the wider globe. They are helped in this way to see education as a means of empowering and equipping themselves to engage in discourse with both their own culture and the rest of the world (Abadiano, 2010).

Villaplaza (2020) discussed that indigenous peoples have a right to high-quality, culturally-respectful education that is safeguarded by a number of international human rights. This right is outlined in the UNESCO Convention. Constantino (2016), on the other hand, noted that "Education is a human right from which IP still do not benefit."

Additionally, Section 28 of the Indigenous Peoples' Rights Act (IPRA) law mandates that "The State shall provide a complete, adequate and integrated system of education, relevant to the needs of the children and young people of ICCs/IPs, through the educational system, public or cultural entities." Section 30 further mandates that "The State shall provide equal access to various cultural opportunities to the ICCs/IPs through the educational system, public or cultural entities." Native children and kids have a right to receive public education at all levels and in all formats.

A new order containing the IP education competencies was published by the Department of Education in 2010 (Department of Education 2010). These competencies include communication skills, critical thinking and problem-solving abilities, sense of self and community, practice of ecological sustainability, and the development of a global worldview. The Department of Education then developed a thorough educational framework for IPs in 2011. In addition to advocating for universal access, the National IP Education Policy Framework works to incorporate indigenous knowledge in the classrooms of IP students by promoting "culture-responsive education for sustainable development," "mother tongue-based multilingual education (MTB-MLE)," and "alternative modes of instructional delivery...to address the peculiar needs of IP learners" (Department of Education 2011).

Wa-Mbaleka(2013) concluded that, teachers need to become familiar with the Katutubo people's culture. Setting up the school in or close to the Katutubo village and incorporating the neighborhood in school progress are also crucial factors. Promoting engaged citizenship is essential to success. He added that the opposing cultural values of the Katutubo people where the root of the two main difficulties teachers had expressed. While education primarily relies on long-term commitment of time and other resources, long-term planning is not part of their ethos. Research conducted by OECD (2017) identified a common formula in schools that are successfully supporting Indigenous students such as,

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an inspirational leader, capable and committed staff, strong relationships with students, parents and local communities, the use of every possible lever to engage and support students to be successful, and sustained commitment to achieve improvements. Additionally, according to the OECD, while it may not be practical for every teacher to meet the needs of indigenous students in terms of language, culture, and identity, there is still much that can be done to support teachers in feeling competent and confident when building relationships with their indigenous students. When there are linguistic or cultural barriers between them and the students they teach, teachers are sometimes unaware of the assumptions they are making about them. When teachers are conscious of their preconceptions, particularly the effect they have on their students, these assumptions can, nevertheless, change.

Systems of education and teacher preparation must find a method to value and validate the knowledge and perceptions of indigenous teachers about indigenous learners and indigenous education. The mentoring of non-indigenous teachers and preservice teachers by indigenous teachers during professional development opportunities is one way this could happen (Santoro et al., 2011).

Teachers' Experiences During Pandemic

In their study, Roth and Jornet (2014) came to the conclusion that teachers can only talk from experience if they have experienced it themselves and have been exposed to it; they only get experience as teachers after going through a lot of meaningful situations.

In the past, teachers were in control of the learners' education. They create lesson plans and deliver lectures and activities in-person. In order for learners to collaborate with one another and have a deeper grasp of their lessons, teachers help the development of communities of inquiry and learning (Marquez et al., 2020).

The research of Robios et al. (2020) noted that IP teachers are evolving toward progressivism. Additionally, they claimed that teachers shared a same vision to guarantee that learners' growth was paramount because it was the most important thing to them and that learning requirements, however diverse, were satisfied.

Bautista et al. (2021) claim that the changes in teaching methods the teachers experienced during the pandemic crisis were abrupt. The Filipino teachers who participated in this study said that their schools gave them adequate support, but there were still issues with infrastructure, teachers' ICT proficiency, professional development, managing students in an online setting, and meeting the objectives outlined in the lesson plans and curricula for the various subjects that they were teaching. Nevertheless, it is comforting to see that despite these issues, the respondents were at ease managing remote classes during the pandemic. In addition, the Filipino teachers were able to adjust to the new ways of working in a virtual learning setting as the return to in-school learning is still in doubt owing to the ongoing threat of COVID-19.

The COVID-19 pandemic, according to Rabacal et al. (2020), is significantly affecting teachers' quality of life (QoL). Nevertheless, despite the moderate to high threat posed by COVID-19, teachers appear to have managed the disease's effects, as evidenced by the mild influence it had on their quality of life in terms of mental health over six months after the nation was placed under a widespread lockdown. The quality of life (QoL) of teachers, along with their physical and mental health, must, however, also be regularly tended to. Additionally, support must be given to teachers as they continue to adjust to the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic.

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VI (June 2024), p.57-103, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

In their survey, Kraft and Simon (2020) emphasized the significant variations in the difficulties brought on by the move to remote teaching and learning. They came to the conclusion that teachers at various stages of their careers, teachers with learners in school, and more experienced teachers had all had difficulties. Along racial and socioeconomic lines, teachers' perceptions of the difficulties their students have faced also differ greatly. By offering supportive working conditions when they are most needed, schools can play a significant part in assisting teachers in overcoming these difficulties.

Many teachers reported feeling physically and emotionally weary, which are well-known signs of burnout, according to Kim and Asbury (2021). Burnout is a result of ongoing stress and can have detrimental effects on teachers, learners, and educational systems, including increased intentions to leave the field and subpar academic results. It is interesting to observe that school administrators have expressed greater anxiety in 2020 than have regular classroom instructors, which is cause for concern for this group and possible repercussions on leadership.

The experiences of PE instructors as they transitioned to online learning at the start of COVID-19 provided crucial information on the near- and maybe long-term state of PE. It is crucial for instructors to come up with alternate techniques to assist learners' standards-based learning since physical educators would no longer be able to teach in the manner in which they had previously been permitted to (face-to-face, using common resources, regularly planned time). The issues of encouraging learners to engage in healthy levels of physical activity and fitness while fostering learner pleasure of such activities persist without the actual presence of the PE teacher. As teachers adjust to guiding learners on a new route toward enabling student learning in PE, ongoing support for PE teachers is required in the form of professional development sessions and additional resources, especially among groups where disparities were discovered (Mercier et al. 2021).

According to the Trust & Whalen (2021) study, educators were unprepared to employ technology for emergency remote teaching during a moment of great need. Even worse, despite the fact that, in theory, technology should have made it simpler to guarantee continuity of learning for students who are enrolled in classes remotely, more than half of the participants identified it as a barrier or a significant obstacle. The results of this investigation indicate that: 1. enhancing pre-service and in-service teacher preparation and assistance in teaching how to recognize, assess critically, and use technologies to support learning in any setting or format (for example, blended, online, remote); 2. expanding all educators' and learners' access to the Internet and high-quality ICT equipment; 3. offering chances for children and their families to advance their technological literacy as part of their education to stop the digital gap from getting worse; 4. presenting chances for teachers, learners, and families to discover the goals, values, and objectives of edtech enterprises and their intertwined relationships with social, economic, political, and cultural contexts; 5. creating chances for instructors and students to learn about mixed and online formats in light of the possibility of future disruptions to the educational system.

Yorgancioglu, 2020 as cited by Boholano & Jamon et al. 2021 emphasized the rapid change from face-to-face teaching to new learning modalities has caused anxiety and fear for policymakers, educators, and teachers.

Among the experiences of teachers who are living in the IP community are: (1) difficulty in workplace, (2) safety and security, (3) learners' habitual behavior, (4) DDU (depressed, dilapidated, & underserved) school, (5) far from the town and difficult roads, (6) teaching the basic literacy, (7) poor learners' achievement, (8) learning modality as a

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Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

challenge, (9) observing health protocols, (10) culture shock, (11) good relationship with the community of non-IP teachers, (12) adjustment of married teachers, (13) giving extrinsic motivation, (14) complex work arrangement during pandemic, (15) exhaustion, and (16) support from stakeholders.

Difficulty in Workplace

Among the experiences of IP and non-IP the teacher-participants, it was in the workplace wherein they found it very challenging, not easy, and difficult to adjust especially at the beginning.

Teachers lack the necessary skills to provide their services as required, despite their best efforts to educate the IPs (Brayboy & Maughan 2009).

Safety and Security

As mentioned in Hughes (2019), Parrett & Budge (2012) noted that the school environment, which encompasses both academic and social difficulties, will be affected if school safety needs are not effectively handled in reference to how to manage and prepare for emergency circumstances. A greater emphasis can be placed on education and student needs when safety planning and preparation are done. A productive school with a positive learning atmosphere is one that is safe, secure, and active.

The presence of the lawless individuals was one of the concerns of teachers wherein they experienced it as a risk in their safety and security. Despite the fact that this dissident group would not directly attack the teachers, their presence and that of the military conveyed the insecurity of the lives of the population, including the teachers.

Learners' Habitual Behavior

According to Macmillan Dictionary (2022), habits and habitual behaviour is a common practice or something that is done a lot and is considered normal. It can also be difficult to learn habitual behavior (Balleine & O'Doherty, 2010).

As participants shared their experiences amidst the IP community, some of them highlighted the habitual behaviour of the learners specifically the learners' floppy attitude inside the classroom caused by tiredness of travelling on foot and learners' absences caused by working during harvest season.

DDU (Depressed, Dilapidated, & Underserved) School

Most of the teachers and learners had the opportunity to spend time in a DDU school. Saludo (2000) defined DDU schools as being deprived, sad, and underserved. In these schools, the only reading resources available to students are outdated books and mimeographed texts with little illustrations or other visuals. There are several dozen books in the library, which is a solitary, decaying shelf in a dimly lit room. There are thousands of them spread out around the Philippines, in areas where children's expectations are dashed before they even learn their ABCs due to extreme poverty, poor transportation, and weather.

Far From the Town and Difficult Roads

According to the report of Navales (2017) in many rural and remote locations, problems such a lack of schools are greater. However, even in cases when there is a school with open classrooms in nearby barangays, there is still a shortage of qualified teachers to be concerned about. Particularly in remote places where physical accessibility to schools can

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obstruct the pursuit of a basic education, students must suffer lengthy distances on foot and face heartbreaking challenges.

Teaching the Basic Literacy

Due to the low mastery of basic literacy among learners in the IP community, teachers find it challenging to educate learners.

The abilities of reading, writing, and mathematics are referred to as basic literacy skills. The development of fundamental reading abilities is thought to be of the utmost importance to improve people's overall quality of life (Kapur, 2019).

Poor Learners' Achievement

Teachers pointed out that they experienced poor learners' achievement before the pandemic.

Human Rights Education in Asian Schools (n.d.) noted that there is a propensity to categorize indigenous pupils as slow learners simply because it takes them longer to acquire the literacy-related skills. It makes sense that it takes longer for students from societies where knowledge is still mostly generated orally to get used to a new communication and thought style.

Learning Modality as a Challenge

One of the experiences teachers in the IP community had shared amid the pandemic is the switch of learning modality caused by the pandemic crisis.

The country's Teachers Dignity Coalition said that the increased strain, health hazards, and expenses brought on by modular distance learning have led to teachers pleading for donations of bond paper and ink to print. These data clearly demonstrate that difficulties can be encountered when using printed self-learning modules (Macaraeg et al., 2021).

Observing Health Protocols

Teachers shared that they are observing health protocols in the highlands especially during the implementation of modular distance learning amid COVID-19 pandemic. With the rising cases, community, especially schools must be complying to the health protocols and maintains them.

All teachers, staff, and students are urged to maintain proper hand hygiene and refrain from touching their faces, according to the USM Home (2022) concept. One of the most crucial steps people may take to stop the spread of COVID-19 is frequent hand washing.

Culture Shock

It cannot be denied that living in the remote places with the indigenous people seems to be shocking. Since of the teacher-participants had a short length of service in the public school and some of them came from the private school, they shared that they experienced culture shock especially in their first time to be immersed in the IP community.

Webster's Dictionary (2002) defined culture as "the customary belief, social forms, and material traits of racial, religious, or social group; also, the characteristic features of everyday existence (such as the diversions or way of life) shared by people in a place or time." Additionally, learning how to handle these demands may be especially crucial for those who

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are new to the field and are learning how to construct lesson plans, convey information in a meaningful way, interact with coworkers, parents, and students, and incorporate demands handed down by superiors.

Beers (2021) emphasized that it is crucial for teachers, especially those who are new to the field, to learn how to manage the demands and are currently learning; how to create lesson plans, deliver information in a meaningful way, interact with coworkers, parents, and students, and incorporate requirements given down by administration—all while learning how to manage 30 students in a classroom setting. Young teachers would benefit from having access to a variety of efficient coping mechanisms in order to become skilled at balancing all of these facets of the profession.

Good Relationship with the Community of Non-IP Teachers

The best way to enhance the teaching and learning process in the IP community is to build good relationships both within and outside the four walls of the classroom.

According to Santoro, Reid, Crawford, and Simpson (2021), it's crucial to create informal networks between parents and teachers outside of the school context where relationships of trust can be built in order to mend the damaged relationship and construct and preserve good school-home partnerships.

According to Robios, Dasig, and Mendoza (2020), strict implementation of the Philippine inclusive education reforms that aim to give everyone access to fair and equitable educational opportunities is possible. According to DepEd Order No. 22, s. 2016, local government shall closely monitor and assess how the National Indigenous Peoples Education Program is being implemented. Additionally, it is important to think about enhancing internal and external stakeholders' involvement. This will improve indigenous students' access to and delivery of high-quality education.

Adjustment of Married Teachers

Married teacher-participants imparted testimonies of the adjustments they had to make when living in the IP community and tensions they experienced leaving home.

To adjust is to successfully and cheerfully integrate into society. According to the expectations of the society in which he or she lives, every member of the society must adjust. Only in society can an individual find fulfillment for their desires. The society is the one who helps them. Adjustment makes life more satisfying. Every stage of life requires adjustment, according to Meenakshi (2017).

Giving Extrinsic Motivation

Motivation from without is not a negative thing. In order to keep people motivated and focused on their goals, external rewards can be a beneficial and successful strategy. This can be especially crucial when individuals are required to finish a task that they find challenging or boring, such as a tiresome project at work (Cherry, 2021).

Complex Work Arrangement During Pandemic

Teachers affirmed that they experienced complex work arrangement during pandemic stating that sometimes they were not able to facilitate well the distribution and retrieval of modules, they cannot accommodate the parents' queries and concerns, and

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VI (June 2024), p.57-103, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

they find it difficult to reproduce modules in their schools due to the unavailability of electricity.

During the term of the COVID-19 pandemic's state of national emergency, government organizations like the DepEd may implement one or more of the alternative work arrangements that the CSC has identified. These include work-from-home options, skeleton staffing, reduced workweeks of four days, staggered work hours, and other unconventional work arrangements. Given the nature of the work/jobs performed by the workers and in accordance with the agency subject to the current community quarantine (DepEd Order (DO) No. O11, s. 2020).

Exhaustion

Teachers experience burnout when they can feel depleted of energy and too exhausted to continue to work. Teacher-participants declared that they experience exhaustion teaching in the IP community before and during the pandemic caused by hours of travel and the reproduction of modules.

Exhaustion is one of the three dimensions of burnout (World Health Organization, 2019).

Support From Stakeholders

Teachers recognized stakeholders' support and involvement during the pandemic particularly on their benevolent assistance in helping the learners' in answering modules.

It is emphasized how crucial it is for students, parents, the community, and administrators to actively participate in the design and implementation of the many school operations. Because modular distance learning is a shared duty, collaboration is crucial (Keim and Olguin, 2009).

Teachers' Coping Mechanism

Teachers employ Lazarus' coping mechanisms every day to deal with potential stressors, according to Ugwuja (2009), referenced by Pagulong & Bulilawa (2021). For instance, if a teacher comes into the potential stressor of a persistently disruptive student, he can use the coping mechanisms to approach the situation in a different way. A teacher who is using confronted coping can go up to the student and ask him to alter his behavior, or he might get in touch with management to handle the pupil. If the teacher distances himself from the class, he would use techniques to ensure that the other students wouldn't be negatively impacted by the kids' behavior. Self-control would be the teacher's ability to control his or her emotions so as not to become overly irritated or lose their cool.

In the study of Magdaraog and Benavides (2019), they pointed out that out-of-field teachers use five coping mechanisms: talk to experienced colleagues, improvise instructional materials, discuss problems, spend money, and reflect to improve.

Teachers had to deal with their own reactions to stress and trauma related to the COVID-19 pandemic as well as those of their students, according to Müller & Goldenberg (2020), as referenced in D'Mello (2021). Given the scope of the COVID-19 pandemic, children were dealing with a wide range of stressful situations, such as distance learning difficulties, living with sick relatives, having little in-person social interaction, grieving the loss of

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a loved one, or going through events that resulted in a significant increase of "49% in calls and contacts to the domestic abuse helpline since the start of the lockdown."

Different difficulties arise for teachers while implementing the modular distant learning modality. These issues were noted based on how instructors planned and prepared the modules, delivered the lessons, gathered data on learner performance, checked and evaluated students' outputs, and gave feedback to students. Teachers can overcome the difficulties they face in the modular distance learning modality by managing their time, coming up with new teaching strategies, adapting to the changes brought about by the new normal trend in education, being flexible, offering alternate plans, being positive and patient, and giving themselves the necessary skills (Castroverde and Acala, 2021).

The study focused on the positive aspects of teaching in public schools, which are rarely studied, particularly during pandemics. The coping techniques and tactics used by instructors were observed in this study. Ten public school teachers were questioned by the researchers. Based on the study's findings, it can be concluded that: (1) most teachers face considerable challenges due to a lack of resources, the management of learners, and the submission and workloads that cause stress and burnout; (2) the advent of the digital age constrained the majority of teachers in public schools. Given the lack of resources, they scarcely manage to carry out specific activities for the students electronically, offer a productive learning environment, and interact with students; (3) public school teachers make due by using the appropriate language and comprehension for their situation; (4) teachers experience success despite pressure and weariness. This includes their enthusiasm, the development of their connections, and the performance of their duties (Robosa, 2021).

In their study, Mari et al. (2021) confirm that during the pandemic, teachers were shown to have more emotion-oriented coping mechanisms than other categories of professionals.

Five key themes about coping mechanisms were cited by De Villa and Manalo (2020) in the context of the new normal prior to the adoption of distance learning. Positive well-being, time management, adaptability to change, peer mentoring, and teamwork are among them. Additionally, they emphasized that despite the challenges that arose during the pre-implementation phase of distance learning, teachers had ways to deal with them in order to meet the demands of the new learning modality and fulfill their duties and responsibilities as learning facilitators.

Synthesis

This review of related literature includes the discussion on the teachers' experiences living in the indigenous peoples community during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Part one, impact of pandemic on education in the indigenous peoples' community, includes studies that list the effects of the pandemic on education, particularly in the IP community.

Part two, teachers' experiences during pandemic, discussed the different research studies that present the experiences of educators during the advent of a pandemic crisis.

Part three, teachers' coping mechanism, covered several research that outline teachers' coping strategies for the difficulties they face.

All of the earlier research that have been reviewed serve as illustrations of studies that are connected to the current study, which focuses on the experiences of the teachers who lived in the IP community during the COVID-19 pandemic.

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Theoretical Framework

The study on teachers' experiences in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) community during the COVID-19 pandemic was anchored on the following theories; Theory of Experience by Dewey, Psychosocial Theory of Erik Erikson, and Cognitive-Motivational-Relational Theory (CMRT) of Coping by Lazarus.

First is the Dewey's Theory of Experience. The Dewey Theory of Experience comes first. Peoples' interactions with the surroundings are influenced by experience, which is a component of their evolutionary make-up. Experience is not at all an individualistic endeavor, even though it occurs within and "on" persons and their bodies. It is mediated by culture, by the active involvement or participation of both younger and older members of society in socially normative activities. Then, experience is something that, in the first place, results from our existence on a planet that, in the words of Berding as cited by Muhit (2013), "must be 'known' in order to be inhabitable. In addition, experience is a truth with two sides, encompassing both the experienced and the experiencing, and it is a result of interactions between living things and their surroundings.

Second theory is the Psychosocial Theory of Erik Erikson that emphasizes the sociocultural determinants of development and presents them as eight stages of psychosocial conflicts (often known as Erikson's stages of psychosocial development) that all individuals must overcome or resolve successfully in order to adjust well to the environment. Erikson's theory suggests that crises can lead to psychosocial growth, but failure to overcome them can have a significant impact (Acero et al., 2004).

The third theory of Cognitive-Motivational-Relational Theory (CMRT) of Coping by Lazarus highlights the role of distinct positive and negative emotions in the stress appraisal process. Essentially, the CMRT links emotion with motivation by arguing that emotions are reactions to the fate of active goal pursuit. The theory of Lazarus as cited in (Pagulong and Bulilawa 2021) pointed out that, managing specific external and/or internal demands that are deemed to be taxing or surpassing a person's resources is referred to as coping, which is a process of ongoing cognitive and behavioral attempts. Coping is merely described as cognitive and behavioral attempts to regulate stress in the definition. To evaluate adaptational results, caring effort must be made regardless of the outcome. The theory of Lazarus which was mentioned by Ntoumanis et al. (2009), motivation is crucial for comprehending cognitive assessments and coping mechanisms in problematic person-environment interactions.

With the aforementioned theories, the researcher was guided and those provided the anchor for the researcher's conduct of the study on teachers' experiences in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) community during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Conceptual Framework

The study aimed to describe teachers' experience in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) community during the COVID-10 pandemic for School Year 2020-2021.

The study conceptualized that the input would be the teachers teaching in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) community. In-depth interview will be the process in determining the teachers' experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic. The foregoing are the researcher's concepts of the study which are graphically illustrated in Figure 1.

The independent variables of the study are twelve (12) Teacher I teachers living in the IP community of the Schools District of Calinog II.

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The dependent variables of the study are the experiences of teachers living in the IP community during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The experiences are identified as difficulty in workplace, safety and security, learners' habitual behaviour, DDU (depressed, dilapidated, & underserved) school, far from the town and difficult roads, teaching the basic literacy, poor learners' achievement, learning modality as a challenge, observing health protocols, culture shock, good relationship with the community of non-IP teachers, adjustment of married teachers, giving extrinsic motivation, complex work arrangement during pandemic, exhaustion, and support from stakeholders.

The antecedent variables are age, sex, position, length of service, marital status, and ethnicity.

Schematic Diagram

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Hypothesized Relationship among the Variables of the Study

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VI (June 2024), p.57-103, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Chapter 3

Research Methodology

This chapter presents the research methods, research design, participants of the study, data-gathering procedures, research instrument, and data analysis that will be used in this study. The purpose of this study was to describe the teachers' experiences living in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) community during the COVID-19 pandemic for School Year 2021-2022.

Research Method

The study used descriptive qualitative method using in-depth interview. During the interview, the interviewer was permitted to sit and reflect on the series of questions regarding a certain topic. The aim was to get the main or the necessary views of the participants in a certain issue in a social context through the responses of the participants to the questions (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2007).

During the interview, the interviewer and interviewee were permitted to sit apart and consider the series of questions regarding a certain topic. Participants were asked to provide their key or fundamental opinions on a certain subject in a social context through their answers to the questions.

Research Design

The study used an ethnographic qualitative research design. Ethnography is the study of particular groups of people, environments, or ways of life. It also refers to the collection of anthropological data (Edith Cowan University, 2021).

In order to closely watch people's behavior and interactions, ethnography is a sort of qualitative research that entails becoming fully immersed in a particular community or organization. The written summary of the research that the ethnographer provides thereafter is also referred to as "ethnography".

It is possible to get a comprehensive grasp of a group's common culture, traditions, and social dynamics through the flexible research approach of ethnography. However, it also presents certain moral and practical difficulties (Caulfield, 2021).

Respondents of the Study

The participants of the study were the twelve (12) purposely chosen teachers from the Schools District of Calinog II, who are living in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) community during the COVID-19 pandemic for School Year 2021-2022.

The respondents were selected based on their availability to furnish the needed data and considering their availability at the time of data gathering.

Sampling Design

Through the use of convenient and purposeful sampling approaches, the respondents were picked. Although this sample does not accurately reflect all teachers, it is deemed sufficient to illustrate the study's qualitative goal.

The purposeful selection of an informant based on the informant's personal characteristics is known as judgment sampling or purposive sampling technique. It is a

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nonrandom technique; therefore, no underlying hypotheses or a predetermined number of informants are required. To put it simply, the researcher selects what information is necessary to have and then searches for sources that can and are willing to share it due to their training or expertise (Bernard 2002, Lewis & Sheppard 2006 as quoted by Tongco, 2007).

Research Instrument

Researcher-made questionnaire was used to gather data. The questionnaire consists open questions designed to gather responses about teachers' experiences. The researcher tailored the questions based on the interest of the study. The questionnaire was divided into 2 parts.

Part I included the respondent's information such as name, school, age, years in service, and ethnicity.

Part II was all about open questions regarding teachers' experiences.

Participants' personal information and information gathered were kept confidential.

Validity of the Research Instrument

Prior to the determination of the validity of the researcher-made questionnaire, each question was submitted for review and modification of the research adviser then by the panel members who are considered experts in their field of research to ensure intelligibility, appropriateness, and relevance.

Validity refers to the appropriateness, meaningfulness, correctness, and usefulness of inferences that a researcher makes. In a content-related evidence of validity, the content and format must be consistent with the definition of variables and sample of subject to be measured and is also helpful in validating the items in the questionnaire (Fraenkel and Wallen, 2007).

Content validity refers to how accurately an assessment or measurement tool taps into the various aspects of the specific construct in question (Content Validity: Definition, Index & Examples, 2015). As a result, Koller (2017), citing de Von et al. (2007), stressed that content validity includes a number of aspects, such as the validity and representativeness of the definition of the construct, the clarity of the instructions, linguistic aspects of the items (such as content, grammar), representativeness of the item pool, and the suitability of the response format. The more precise a test's measurement of the target constructs, the better its content validity. The adjustments, remarks, and recommendations made by the panel of validators in relation to the research questionnaire were taken into account and implemented using the Eight-Point Criteria for Content Validation by Good and Scates.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher secured permits from the thesis adviser, from the Dean of the Graduate School department of University of Iloilo, PHINMA, Schools Division Superintendent of the Schools Division of Iloilo, Public Schools District Supervisor, and School Head of the Schools District of Calinog II.

Permits from the individual participants were handed over to allow the researcher to conduct the study. The researcher personally went to the school, community, or place convenient to the participants to conduct the interview following the minimum health protocol standards required by the Inter Agency Task Force (IATF), Local Government Unit (LGU) of the Municipality of Calinog, and the Department of Education (DepEd).

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The researcher engaged in participant observation in order to gain insight into the culture in which she was immersed. The researcher described the participants' daily routines and pursuits in the selected environment. The study's basic structure mixed open-ended narrative with observation. The researcher also supplemented her participant observation data by speaking with individuals who could help her comprehend the setting or group she was researching. The researcher and the participants conducted an in-depth interview.

The researcher created a list of all potential questions before beginning to interview participants and then determined which ones were most closely linked to the research question. Open-ended questions were created to allow the participant to express themselves from their point of view.

During the interview, the researcher used audio and video recording to fully record the whole process of interview. The utilization of audio and video sought approval from the participant and was kept for privacy.

The response and collected answers or information from the participants were consolidated after series of interviews, and finally was analyzed.

Data Analyses

Questionnaires were reproduced according to the number of respondents of the study. Personal information were gathered, organized, and consolidated. Responses from the series of in-depth interview were audio and video recorded. Responses from the interview were analyzed using the thematic analysis.

A technique for assessing qualitative data is thematic analysis. Usually, it refers to a group of texts, such the transcripts of interviews. The researcher carefully analyses the data to find recurring themes, subjects, concepts, and patterns of meaning (Caulfield, 2019).

Chapter 4

Data Presentation, Interpretation, and Analyses

This chapter presents the findings of the study. It presents the descriptive-qualitative analyses of the teachers' experiences living in the indigenous people community before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the Schools District of Calinog II for school year 2021-2022.

Specifically, this sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of teacher-participants in terms of age, sex, position, length of service, marital status, & ethnicity?
2. What are the experiences of teachers who are living in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) community?
3. What policy can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

Profile of the teachers

Rice (2003) held that a student's teacher matters. In actuality, it is the primary educational component impacting student accomplishment.

Furthermore, according to Darling-Hammond (2000), teacher quality indicators have a stronger correlation with student accomplishment than other types of educational

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investments including smaller class sizes, overall education spending, and teacher compensation.

Profiling teachers is essential to information about a person based on known traits or tendencies that may be a basis for measure of teacher quality.

In the study, 12 public elementary school teachers from the Schools District of Calinog II in the Municipality of Calinog who are teaching on the IP community were the participants of the study.

Participant 1, a Teacher I, is a 30-year-old single IP teacher who has been in service for three years. Participant 2, a Teacher I, is a 24-year-old single non-IP teacher who is in teaching for two years.

Participant 3, a Teacher I, is 30-year-old single IP teacher who has been teaching for three years.

Participant 4, a Teacher I, is a 26-year-old single IP teacher teaching for two years.

Participant 5, a Teacher I, is a 29-year-old married non-IP teacher who has been serving for three years.

Participant 6, a Teacher I, is a 29-year-old non-IP teacher who has been in service for two years. Participant 7, a Teacher I, is a 34-year-old single IP teacher who has five years of teaching experience.

Participant 8, a Teacher I, is a 28-year-old married IP teacher who has 6 years of teaching experience.

Participant 9, a Teacher I, is a 38-year-old non-IP teacher who has been in service for seven years. Participant 10, a Teacher I, is a 32-year-old single non-IP teacher with six years of teaching experience.

Participant 11, a Teacher I, is a 29-year-old married IP teacher who has been teaching for six years. She had a position of Teacher I.

Participant 12, a Teacher I, is a 31-year-old married non-IP teacher with five years teaching experience.

Most of the teacher participants are young adults, and most of them are female. All of them are Teachers I. Most of them had a short length of service. Most of them are single. Seven of them are non-IPs, and five are IPs.

From the data collected on the experiences of the participants, sixteen (16) main themes emerged.

Teachers' Experiences in Teaching in the Indigenous Peoples (IP) Community

Numerous teachers in the community of Indigenous Peoples have shared their experiences both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. The experiences of teachers extend beyond the four walls of the classroom and are not just confined there.

The participants' replies during the in-depth interviews helped to paint a fuller picture of the teachers' experiences living in the Indigenous People's community.

Based on the results of the interview conducted to the participants, the experiences identified by them were difficulty in workplace, safety and security, learners' habitual behavior, DDU (depressed, dilapidated, & underserved) school, far from the town and difficult roads, teaching the basic literacy, poor learners' achievement, learning modality as a challenge, observing health protocols, culture shock, good relationship with the community of non-IP teachers, adjustment of married teachers, giving extrinsic motivation, complex work arrangement during pandemic, exhaustion, and support from stakeholders.

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Difficulty in Workplace

Despite their best intentions to educate the IPs teachers have inadequate knowledge on how to deliver their services as it was expected (Brayboy & Maughan 2009).

Among the experiences of IP and non-IP the teacher-participants, it was in the workplace wherein they found it very challenging, not easy, and difficult to adjust especially at the beginning.

According to Participant 1, "So before the COVID-19... uhm... teaching in the IP community is an honor for me since I came from the same tribe or the same group and... uh... it is an honor, and I am proud to give back to the community where I came from. So *ang pagtudlo* (teaching them) *kananda* especially sa *Aglonok Primary School sa last primary school medyo a quite challenge and... uh... it takes a lot of... uh... encouragement, inspiration, commitment, and passion para sa kananda. It's because nga tuya sa bukid mo maintindihan kon ano ka-simple ang pagpangabuhin and then kung ano ka-simple ang anda nga way of living everyday... kag didto mo man maintindihan kung paano nanda hatagan sang importansya ang edukasyon* (This makes it particularly difficult for them at Aglonok Primary School, the last primary school, and... it takes a lot of encouragement, inspiration, devotion, and passion for them. It's because you'll see how simple life is in the highlands and how simple their daily lives are there, and you'll also see how important education is to them)."

Participant 4 added, "Teaching in the IP community is not easy like a pie..."

As a teacher, you should put yourself in that situation that "*ubrahon ko daya, kaya ko daya hay teacher ako*" (I will do this, I can do this, because I am a teacher). So, *mas maging effective ikaw kung ginapursige mo sa self mo nga kayanon mo daya* (If you can show yourself that you can accomplish this, you're effective)."

Participant 6 said, "So knowing and having seen their sacrifices really motivated me to the best that I can and... uhh *bisan naka-experience ako nga mabudlay ang aragyan noh kag ang sitwasyon ka school kag bisan ya mga* (eventhough I experienced difficult roads and the school's situation and even the) *people nga* (that) it's very hard to handle. *Ginahambal ko sa kaugalingon ko nga* (I tell myself that) it's all worth it. *Ya kabudlay ka* (The struggle of the) *teacher waay gid gani daa it kamalingking sa kabudlay ka mga bata* (is nothing compared to the struggle of the learners)."

In addition, Participant 7 stated, "So before the COVID-19 pandemic I have much challenging experiences in teaching the indigenous people community like riding in motorcycle and walking in slippery and muddy road to reach the school."

Participant 8 believed, "Teaching in the IP community and teaching on the lowlands can never be compared as the same. It is always been difficult for us in the previous years, especially sa *pag-adto mo pa lang diya* (especially when you arrive here). So sa *experience mo pa lang nga ikaw naga-adto sa eskwelahan* (in your experience going to school), how much more *ang mga bata nga nagapanaw tigpira ka kilometres, waay pa kapamahaw* (those children who are walking how many kilometres, without having breakfast)."

Participant 10 asserted, "So my teaching experience in the IP Community before the pandemic is very challenging because every day I had seen the struggles of my learners to teach them with an empty stomach."

Participant 12 also mentioned that teaching before the pandemic is not that easy at all.

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These results corroborate Hewitt's (2006) assertion that instructors working to promote education in the indigenous population faced systemic challenges. Their contacts with others whose cultures are wholly different from their own is a contributing element in their lack of physical safety. These factors led the teachers to prepare for such circumstances.

Safety and Security

How successfully a teacher will be able to do his or her duties at the school will be greatly influenced by their level of safety at work. Before a teacher to contribute to the success of the educational system, that person must feel secure. For a teacher to freely contribute to the goals and objectives of the school, their safety at work is crucial (Eseyin et al., 2017).

Teachers were concerned about the lawless individuals' presence because they perceived it as a risk. Although this dissident group would not attack the instructors directly, their presence and that of the military communicated the danger to the population's lives, including the teachers'.

Participant 1 told his experience regarding risk saying, "...it's because *nga ang* (the) area is... uhm... NPA-dominated, so *kumbaga gamay lang gid nga...* uh... encourage *kanada is masaylo don sanda or ma-join sanda sa group. So kinanglan bata pa is tudluan mo dun sanda kung paano mangin responsible nanda... responsibility nanda nga* how to love their country as well as *nga para ma-realize nanda nga 'ay waay kami ginpabay-an kang gobyerno, ay as an IP damo gali kami opportunity, damo gali ginahatag kanamon nga benefits para nga kami mabuligan kag makatapos sa urihi* (That means they might join the group once they are encouraged. So you need to teach them at an early age the responsibility of loving their country so that they will realize that the government does not disregard them, that as an IP they have opportunities, and that more benefits are given to help them to finish their studies someday)."

Participant 2 shared, "...another challenge *pa gid ang mga NPA bala, Ma'am* (is the so called NPA)... *nga ang risk sa teacher nga for example may engkwentro between AFP and NPA amu gid daa ang number one nga risk kanamon hay ti paano dulang kami karon kon madisgrasya kami bala sa bukid* (the teacher's risk, for example, that there would be an encounter, what would happen to us if we met an accident on the highlands)."

Participant 10 also added, "*May mga dyan man kuno sa palibot namon nga naga-panilag man nga mga NPA pero kung sa personal waay man gid namon sanda nakita, since ano man sanda pareho man kanamon nga naga-adto sa eskwelahan ukon sa palibot* (There is hearsay within the community that there are NPAs who keep an eye on us, but we don't really see them personally since, like us, they also come to school) *kag may mga Armed Forces man nga ga-stay sa eskwelahan, so amu da kis-a daw ka risky man. Kaagi gani nga may duty kami, may nagalinupok lang nga canyon nanda so as tawo man kami kulbaan man hay maka-enconter kaw ka mga linupok marapit sa barangay hall* (and there are members of the Armed Forces who stay at school, so sometimes it is very risky also. This time, we are on duty, and there were canyon explosions of them [AFP], so as individuals, we feel nervous because we encounter blasts that seem so near)."

According to Participant 11, "*May dyan pa gid nga time nga once magsaka don kami sa bukid tapos nataw-an kami ka impormasyon nga indi anay magsaka hay tungod may mga NPA, may nagsaka tuya nga army. Te once mga magsumalangay sanda*

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International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VI (June 2024), p.57-103, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

sigurado gid nga may ambush te delikado kami nga mga teachers (There are also times when we are about to go to the highlands and we receive information to postpone our duty because there are NPAs and armies there, too. So once they meet, surely there will be an ambush, so it is dangerous for us teachers)."

Participant 12 also stressed, "*Isa pa gid nga challenge ang mga external threats bala like basi may mga ambush rapit sa school* (One more challenge is the external threat of ambush near the school). Te hugot lang gid nga pangamuyo kag mangkot gid sa mga superior kon ano ang mayad nga himuon, kon masaka bala kami or ma-hulat lang magtawhay (So, we just keep our faith strong, and we ask our superiors what they do best: if we will go to school or wait for everything to appease)."

These results lend credence to Zinn's (2016) risk theory. It states that risk should be avoided or minimized, and it offers the knowledge that some benefits can only be obtained by taking risks. There are at least three main approaches to managing risk: instrumental rationalism, which is supported by expert information; non-rational approaches, like hope or faith; and intermediate approaches, like trust, intuition, and emotion, which are based on experience and tacit knowledge.

Learners' Habitual Behavior

As members in the IP community shared their experiences, several of them emphasized the regular behavior of the students, particularly the students' sluggish mood inside the classroom caused by fatigue from walking, and the students' absences caused by working during harvest season.

According to Macmillan Dictionary (2022), habits and habitual behaviour is a common practice or something that is done a lot and is considered normal. It can also be difficult to learn habitual behavior (Balleine & O'Doherty, 2010).

Participant 4 expressed his experience on learners' habitual behavior saying "They [learners] are just walking to school, and they are already too tired to listen and learn well when the class is going on."

According to Participant 6, "I entered at the service 2019 and it was the year before the pandemic I have witnessed and experienced how the learners strive to go to school every day. I witnessed their sacrifices, waking up early in the morning, walking at least three hours a day and... uhh... handling their hunger and sleepiness in the class."

On the other note, Participant 7 added, "Most of the pupils came from the adjacent barangays... so always *gid* they look haggard and sleepy when they arrive. It really needs patience in dealing those pupils during class hours..."

Participant 8 shared, "*So ang pinaka-challenge gid guro* (the most challenging) on my experience in 6 years, how would you deal *sa mga bata nga pag-abot sa classroom waay don ti focus kanimo* (to those learners who don't have their focus on you anymore when they arrive in the classroom), *waay don ang attention kanimo hay syempre gutom don sanda, ang iban tana natuyo don* (the attention is not on you anymore since they are already starving; others are already sleepy)."

Participant 9 also confirmed, "*Dasun, experience ko pa gid nga ang mga kabataan eventhough sa sulod ka classroom, makit-an mo gid sanda nga daw kulang gid sa pagkaon kay te bisan naga-klase ikaw kis-a ang iba makit-an mo gid nga waay kapamahaw, gaparanghuy-ab, dasun daw nakutoy pa gid sanda hay te marayo man ang eskwelahan halin a balay nanda* (Then, I also experienced that learners inside the class, you can really

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Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

see that they lack food because even having class, sometimes you see them without breakfast, yawning, and then very tired since their houses are far from school)."

Furthermore, Participant 10 stressed, "So *may mga estudyante kami, Ma'am nga naga-adto lang sa eskwelahan nga kis-a waay ti balon...* (We have learners that go to school without packed food sometimes, and if even having packed food...). So this can affect the learning performance of the learners."

Participant 11 mentioned, "The second thing is the absences of the learners most especially during planting and harvest season of their crops *kapin pa kon tigparanggas ka ginatawag nga Malido, tanom nanda nga Palawan* (especially during the planting of the 'Malido', the 'Palawan')"

Participant 12 added, "Another one is, some of the learners come to school with an empty stomach. So how can they be attentive and absorb the lesson *kon gadinaguok busong da? Hindi man tanan, pero maluoy ka gid hay may pagkaon man sanda pay natunga nanda sa recess kag igma, kis-a recess gani ubos don. Tapos, mantika pa dapli ka iban, may mais man kag kon ano lang nga may dyan sanda* (if they are starving? Not all, but you will really feel pity because if they have food, they allow it for recess and lunch; sometimes it's good for recess only. Then, others have cooking oil, corn, and anything else they have as a source.)."

These results confirm the findings of Dayaganon's (2015) study, which found that indigenous pupils used to walk a distance from their homes to school. They discovered that the reason students consistently arrive late and eventually miss class is an avoidable truth. The Non-IP teachers were irritated by this issue. Furthermore, children are typically expected in the fields at harvest season in rural communities, according to Weinstein (2010). They missed two or three months of school so they could drop out and repeat the grade.

DDU (Depressed, Dilapidated, & Underserved) School

Saludo (2000) described DDU schools — deprived, depressed and underserved as schools that the only reading resources available to students are outdated books and mimeographed texts with little illustrations or other visuals. There are several dozen books in the library, which is a solitary, decaying shelf in a dimly lit room. There are thousands of them spread out around the Philippines, in areas where children's expectations are dashed before they even learn their ABCs due to extreme poverty, poor transportation, and weather.

According to the responses of the participants, they experienced inadequate access from services and resources such as electricity, internet connection and equipment, and materials for learning while living and teaching in the IP community.

According to Participant 1, "So *una ko didto nga pag-assign* (my first assignment there) wayback 2018, so *ang* (the) Aglonok Primary School is... uh... as I can... uh... explain or I can imagine it as a dying school *kay gamay lang gid ang estudyante* (because there are only few learners) almost 15 and then *ang wala sila* (they don't have) uniform, *wala sila* (they don't have) school supplies, *wala sila gamit pang-eskwelahan* (they don't have stuffs for school)."

Participant 2 also affirmed by saying, "Uhm... lack of supplies. *Syempre challenge don daa sa pagtudlo kon waay ikaw enough nga resources sa imu nga community sa imu nga palibot* (Of course, it's already a challenge to teach if you don't have enough resources

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Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

within the community.). *Paano ka makatudlo it effective (How would you teach effectively)?*"

Participant 3 stated that, prior to the pandemic, they had to spend five days in the barangay because they were a teacher in a far-flung barangay school. They must therefore adapt to situations when there is no electricity and no internet.

For Participant 4, "Here in our school, there's a big, a lot of difference here because they [learners] can't research or study well because they don't have electricity or proper lighting to study well."

Participant 5 highlighted, "The most challenging part living in an IP community before and after this pandemic is my adaptation. So this challenge specifically focuses on the adaptation on my preparation of my lessons although the new system of education is highly supported by technology. So *diya man kanaton sa bukid, Ma'am, man-an mo man diba nga waay ti kuryente di, so mabudlay para kanamon ang magdara ka mga* (here on the highland, you know that there's no electricity, so it's hard for us to bring) equipment *bala* like television. So the availability of the power and this equipment are highly incapacitated."

According to Participant 7, "...*diya sa atun sa Supanga* (here in Supanga) we are lacking and limited internet connection, lack of gadgets to be used by learners and many others."

Participant 10 shared, "It's super challenging as an ICT coordinator I am the one to facilitate the submission of different online reports and provide technical assistance to my school head, class advisers and to my co-teachers with regard to ICT. Before pandemic, our problem is the unstable internet connection. So, *sa amon eskwelahan waay ka gid gawa ti makita nga signal mu daa kis-a delayed kami sa pag-submit ka amon reports* (in our school, you can barely acquire a signal, which is why we're sometimes delayed in submitting our reports.). *So maman-an lang namon daa nga may reports kami kung makapabanwa don kami, kon makauli don kami kada Friday* (We will just know if there are reports when we already reach the town when we reach our homes on Fridays)."

Participant 12 also told that, "Another is *ang* (the) submission *ka* (of) urgent online reports... *Dugangan pa ka* (plus the) signal *nga tama ka hina* (that is very weak) so we can't receive updates immediately. Yes, *nagprovide man gid ka simcard ang DepEd pero indi man namon mapuslan kon diya kami sa takas* (the DepEd provided simcard, however it's still useless if we're on the highland)."

Isa pa gid (Another thing), lack of budget for supplies and materials for learning, since I know *nga indi man tanan nga* (not everything from the) budget *sa* (of) MOOE *nakalaan* (is intended) for supplies *lang* (only)."

These results provide credence to Hennin's (2020) report on removing obstacles to education experienced by indigenous peoples during the pandemic, which claims that the Indigenous Navigator data provides an overview of the infrastructure and equipment deficiencies in indigenous schools. There have been numerous reports of internet access being unavailable at schools in various places all around the world.

Furthermore, according to research conducted by Sy and Rahemtulla et al. (2021), it was found that only 83% of Filipinos reside in locations with adequate fixed broadband speeds, while just 70% do so for mobile. The ratio drops to 70% of the rural population using fixed broadband and 52% using mobile when they narrow that down to the population in barangays classified as rural by administrative border data. Additionally, they noted that in the Philippines, connection is still higher in urban areas and persists in more rural areas with limited digital infrastructures. The effects of the epidemic, in addition to the

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ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

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National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

restrictive environment and low levels of competition, have made ICT policy interventions even more difficult. The digital environment has turned productivity into a luxury, and individuals who lack adequate access are left behind, missing out on possibilities for everything from basic necessities and high-quality education to respectable employment and reskilling. The issues facing the Philippines and other nations in providing availability, accessibility, and affordability of dependable internet have never been higher in the post-COVID-19 world.

Far from the Town & Difficult Roads

According to Navales' research from 2017, there are more issues in many rural and remote places, such as a lack of schools, but even in cases where there is a school with open classrooms in nearby barangays, there is still a shortage of qualified teachers to be concerned about. Particularly in remote locations where physical accessibility to schools can obstruct the pursuit of a basic education, students must suffer lengthy distances on foot and face heartbreaking challenges.

In participants' views, the reality of living in the IP community was that they lived a significant distance from the town and travelled difficult and risky rough roads to reach their schools.

Participant 1 explained, "...so even *ang* (the) instructional materials *daw mabudlay ka pa magdara* (are difficult to transport) it's because *nga karayo kay kailanglan mo pa magsakay sa motor it isa ka oras* and then *panawon mo duman halin sa Brgy. Supanga padto sa Aglonok sang tatlo tubtob apat ka oras nga pagpanaw* (it's very far and you need to ride the motorcycle for one hour then you'll walk from Brgy. Supanga going to Aglonok for three to four hours)."

Participant 2 imparted, "*Naga-stay gid kami 1 week gid tana* (we are staying there for a week). *Maabot kami Monday* (we arrive on Monday) and then *madulhog duman kami* (we will go home on) Friday. *Pero sa Monday nga ran* (However on Monday)... *te ma-travel kami sa motor 1 hour and 30 mins pa abi dayon ma-walk pa kami 3-4 hours sa amon nga school* (we still travel through motorcycle for 1 hour and 30 minutes and then we will walk 3-4 hours going to our school)."

Participant 3 added, "Supanga Elementary School is located also at Brgy. Supanga and you have to ride the motorcycle for almost one hour and the road is uhhh... *tama ka lutak* (very muddy) especially *kon mauran* (when it rains)."

Participant 8 believes that there are a lot of challenges especially on her part. She added, "*Ang aton eskwelahan is tawag bala nga marayo* (our school is far), *indi mo dayon ma-sulod-sulod especially sang una nga waay pa ti mga sementado* (you cannot reach it immediately, especially before the road is cemented)."

According to Participant 10, "So one of the challenges in the IP community is the transportation from home to school, since *nga kis-a sa banwa man kami gauli so budlay nga mag-travel pakadto sa school*(sometimes we stay at the town so it is hard to travel going to school). And since *ang amon eskwelahan* (our school) there is no electricity, so *mabudlay man* (it is also difficult) *mag-travel ka* (to travel) *modules paadto sa eskwelahan* (going to school)."

Participant 11 admitted, "Another one is my transportation because of the difficult roads going to school and going home especially when the weather is not good. Regarding my transportation, it became more difficult also because before we only carry 2-3 bags and

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during this pandemic we added modules that are good for 1 or 2 weeks since we cannot print in our school because we don't have electricity."

These findings support the study of (Quijada & Orale 2018) which shows that novice teachers in remote areas need to endure the uncomfortable and less safe modes of transportations to reach their destination.

Teaching the Basic Literacy

The abilities of reading, writing, and mathematics are referred to as basic literacy skills. Basic literacy skills are seen to be extremely important for improving people's life generally (Kapur, 2019).

The teacher-participants brought up that they experienced to teach the basic literacy before and during the pandemic.

Participant 1 shared his experience to teach the basic literacy by saying, "But as an IP... uh... *kinahanglan mo intindihon nga kailangan mo mag-provide kananda sang kalidad nga edukasyon at least sa urihi indi man sanda pagtuntuhon ka mga tawo* (I need to understand that I need to provide them with quality education so that at least someday people will not deceive them). So *unang-una* (first of all), is *gin-ubra ko didto* (what I did there) is *ang pagtudlo kananda halin sa* (I started to teach them the) basic ..."

According to Participant 2, "*Paano ako magtudlo ka daya?* (How would I teach?) *Mangin effective teacher ayhan ako* (Would I become an effective teacher)? So *nag-umpisa gid ako sa* (I started with the) basic."

Participant 3 added, "It is sad that their parents could not teach them because some of the parents there did not finish their schooling, but I am telling them that just focus on reading and counting *hay amu da ang importante muh* (because that's important). Later on *pwede ta ma-refresh ang lesson once ang klase magbalik don pero ya bata mabudlayan kon indi kamaan magbasa kag magsulat* (we could refresh the lesson once the classes have already returned, but the learner will have difficulty if he or she does not know how to read and write)."

For Participant 11, "*...napangtaw-an ko lang sanda ka LAS, for example mga tracing letters, numbers, kapin pa gid sa anda nga ngaran* (I just give them LAS (Learning Activity Sheets), like letter and number-tracing, especially tracing their names)."

These results back up the SIL Philippines report from 2022, which states that while the Philippines has a basic literacy rate of above 88.5%, there are still certain areas of illiteracy.

Additionally, according to UNESCO (2000), indigenous peoples received basic literacy training so they could learn to write their names.

Poor Learners' Achievement

There is a propensity to categorize indigenous pupils as slow learners simply because it takes them longer for them to pick up the skills necessary for literacy, according to Human Rights Education in Asian Schools (n.d.). It makes sense that it takes longer for students from societies where knowledge is still mostly generated orally to get used to a new communication and thought style.

Teachers pointed out that they experienced poor learners' achievement before the pandemic.

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World Education Connect

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Volume IV, Issue VI (June 2024), p.57-103, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Participant 2 experienced highlighted, "When it comes to teaching *gid tana* very delay *gid amon mga bata sa bukid* (our learners on the highlands are very delayed), honestly speaking. *Kumbaga maribit gid amon mga bata diya sa lowland because anda parents mga indi man kamaan magbasa kag magsulat* (In other words, because their parents are also illiterate, our students are performing worse than those in the lowlands)."

According to Participant 7, "Many pupils were slow learners and some were non-readers so *sa part namon* (in our part) as a teacher we really need to exert extra time and effort in doing a remediation. It is quite difficult..."

Participant 8 explained, "*Sang una, sang indi pa sanda ma-reach di ka civilization, manubo gid man tana eh hay ti sang una tana pag indi dun gani sanda kalab-ot sa higher grade, mamana don, maubra don* (Prior to the arrival of civilization, their literacy was extremely poor since they would marry and start working as soon as they finished the lower grades)."

For Participant 9, "...*sa sulod ka classroom tama gid sanda ka-mahina dasun daw kabudlay kananda tudluan it's because nga ang mga parents nanda mga previous years nanda nga mga ginikanan, mga kalolohan pa gid nanda waay naka-eskwela* (they learn very slowly in class, which makes it challenging to teach them because neither their parents nor their grandparents went to school)."

Participant 12 also highlighted, "In terms of teaching, it poses a great deal of challenge because I can say that the level of literacy and numeracy skills of the learners is poor. We are having the yearly assessment in reading and numeracy wherein the result shows that many of the learners are highly-challenged in these areas."

These results back up Gonzales's report from 2019 that, in addition to NAT results, DepEd also released the most recent PISA results from the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), in which Filipino students scored near the bottom in science and mathematics and last out of 79 participating nations.

During the pandemic, teachers mentioned that the learners' achievement is still a concern and became more challenging.

According to Ingle (2022), the Indigenous Peoples' Education Office (IPsEO) and IP Education Focal Persons across the nation have been thinking about solutions to the problem of how to get children access to learning resources as well as how to help them use those materials. Like everywhere else in the nation, parents and other family members will play a significant part in helping young children. However, for IP communities, individuals typically have low levels of literacy and formal education, making this position more difficult.

Participant 1 experienced poor learners' achievement during pandemic by stressing, "...*nakita namon nga daw slow ang anda nga pag-develop, kumbaga gamay lang ang nabal-an sang bata... kag ang module is indi man siya effective* (we've seen that their development is slow; in other words, the learners only know a few... and the module is ineffective)."

Participant 2 also shared, "*So ang challenge gid kanamon in teaching during the pandemic nga daw waay gawa gid it development sa mga bata* (The challenge for us in teaching during the pandemic is that it seems that there is no development for the learners) so *kumbaga ang learning daw waay nag-takes place sa bata, daw mas nagbudlay... makita mo gid nga waay ti development during the pandemic sa amon tuya sa area namon* (in other words, learning doesn't take place, seems that it has become more difficult. You can see that during the pandemic in our area, there has been no development)."

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DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

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According to Participant 3, "*Feeling ko daya nga pandemic especially nga waay ti nagatudlo kananda hay syempre busy man anda mga parents sa panguma kag waay sanda ti source. Only source nanda is ya ma-share ka teacher nga knowledge hay syempre waay sanda it mga tv, mga internet (I think that during this pandemic, especially since no one educates them [learners], they don't have the source since their parents are too busy farming. They don't have access to television or the internet, therefore their main source of information is their teacher)... you know... I think that's the difficulty nga feeling ko kung magbalik ya face to face you have to go back from the basic (that we have to go back to the basic if face-to-face will start).*"

Participant 4 added, "...during this pandemic because we can't have face-to-face classes daw indi naton sila makita don, daw indi mo makita ang ila progress kung diin don asta ang anda development (it seems that we can't see their [learners] progress, if what is the level of their development)."

For Participant 5, "Uhm... my teaching experience during this COVID-19 pandemic is full of challenges that test my resiliency as an effective teacher. During the prohibition of the face-to-face class, I know that my problems to my learners are highly-challenged most especially in the reading skills which is... uhm a top issue in an IP community."

Participant 6 pointed out, "During this pandemic naman nga modular kita hindi naton matungkad ang assessment kung ano ya learnings ka bata so nagabase lang kita sa module (that we are on modular, we cannot measure the assessment if what are the learnings of the learners so we only base on modules) and it's very hard to assess the learnings of the learners nga indi mo sanda makita especially sa kinder (especially in kindergarten)."

According to Participant 7, "*Sa modular learning tana naga-base lang kita sa mga modules (we only base from modules). Indi mo ma-assess kon bala ano gid ang level ka kinaaram ka imo bata (You cannot exactly assess what is your learner's level of knowledge).*"

Participant 8 highlighted, "*Pag-umpisa duman ka pandemic nga daya, syempre ang iban pagbati nanda nga "ay modular te di tamon kamaan magsabat te di dulang tamon mag-eskwela"* (Others who heard about this pandemic at the time said, "What would happen to us because we don't know how to answer?"). *Ang iban indi don kamaan magsulat, ang iban di don kamaan magbasa. Nagakalimtan don nanda kung ano ya gintun-an nanda sang nagliligad* (Others lack even the fundamentals of writing and reading. Their prior knowledge has already been forgotten)."

Participant 9 emphasized, "*Sa pandemic pa gid nga dya, ang mga kabataan daw nagblangko dun gid matyag ko anda nga ulo bala haw* (It seems to me that students' minds are already blank during this pandemic) *...daw nagtuktukon hay te waay don sanda naga-atubang sa mga teachers dasun makit-an mo kis-a gani ang iba daw indi don kamaan magsulat ka ngaran da sa modules nanda bala* (others occasionally struggle to write their names on their modules, suggesting that their memory has become rusty)."

Participant 12 added, "*...ang modules daw indi gid masarangan ka learners namon hay kalabanan kananda pigado gani sanda sa paghangop ka simple nga leksyon* (the majority of our learners struggle to understand even basic lectures, hence they are unable to complete the modules). *Te bisan MELC pa daa nga tawag, behind gid amon kabataan sa takas* (Therefore, despite the so-called MELC, our students in the highlands are still falling behind). Regarding the achievement, I can say that before the pandemic, my learners' achievement in reading and numeracy is better if compared during this pandemic."

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Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

These results support the research of Kearns (2012), who found that teachers were concerned about the equality of assessment between face-to-face and distance learning. They wanted to make sure that the students were taking the tests in the same circumstances and that they could submit comparable written works and other objective-attainment indicators.

School closures have already been attributed to a rise in dropout rates and decreased literacy, and the World Bank estimates that the number of children aged 10 and below, from low-and middle-income countries, who cannot read simple text has increased from 53% prior to the pandemic to 70% today. Furthermore, according to De Guzman (2021), UNICEF warns that COVID-19 will be impacting the mental health of children and young adolescents for years to come. De Guzman (2021) also cited a report from March 2021 in which it was discovered that 86% of the 1,299 students surveyed by the Movement for Safe, Equitable, Quality, and Relevant Education said they learned less through the education department's take-home modules; this percentage was also true for 66% of those who used online learning and 74% of those who used a combination of online learning and hard-copy material.

Learning Modality as a Challenge

According to the nation's Teachers Dignity Coalition, modular distance learning has increased teachers' workloads, health hazards, and costs, forcing them to beg for donations of bond paper and ink to print. These only conclusively demonstrate that using printed self-learning modules presents difficulties. Macaraeg et al. (2021) as stated in [Pentang et al. \(2022\)](#)

One of the experiences teachers had shared amid the pandemic is the challenging learning modality.

Regarding the learning modality, Participant 1 said, "*Sa pag-decide pa lang sa kung ano nga modality ang itudlo kananda nga maka-suit kag maka-cover up man sanda nga indi man sanda maurihi so a quite challenge don kanamon as a teacher (Finding a modality that will work for them [learners] so that they won't fall behind is already a difficulty for us teachers). So, nag-come-up sa printed modular learning modality. So although nga bal-an namon nga indi gid siya... kumbaga indi gid sanda maka-cope up (So we came up with printed modular learning modality although we know that they can't cope up with it).*"

Participant 2 added, "*Sa modules gid tana Ma'am challenge pa gid kanamon hay ti during the pandemic, masaka kami Monday to Wednesday. Thursday kami manaog hay ma-print duman kami ka modules pagka-Friday. (We find the modules challenging because we will go to the highlands on Monday to Wednesday and on Thursday we will go home because we have to print modules on Fridays). Kumbaga daw nagdugang amon nga urubrahon, instead daad nga i-print pa namon, daad ginatudlo pa namon sa mga learners (In other words, it's additional work for us; instead of printing, supposedly it's time to teach our learners.)*"

Furthermore Participant 3 added to the thought, "So teaching during the pandemic... I think I feel useless. You know because your worth as a teacher was not given totally to the... uuh learners because they are just modular. *Feeling mo indi mo matao ya 100% mo nga i-impart kananda (You believe that you are not capable of providing your all) so it was sad and until now I feel useless as a teacher.*"

Participant 4 also claimed, "My experience in teaching in IP community during COVID-19 has lot of challenges because you can't have face-to-face classes and can't

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interact with your learner... *kung para lang man kanakon gusto ko duman mag-face-to-face para gid sa kabataan naton para makita naton nga indi don sanda mabudlayan* (I wish to meet with our students face-to-face so they won't suffer any longer)."

For Participant 6, "So during the pandemic, it challenged all of us, *nag-challenge sa* (It challenged the) teacher, *sa* (the) learner, and ofcourse the parents. The set-up in school which is the modular learning challenged the teachers, the parents, especially the learners. Adapting to this new normal is very hard."

For Participant 7, "Having the modular classes is very hard because most of the parents are not literate and are not able to help their children to answer their module."

Moreover, Participant 8 asserted, "*Sa una nga waay pa ti pandemic mabudlay don nga daan* (before the pandemic, it's already tough). *Mas nagbudlay pa gid pag-pandemic since ang mga parents reliant lang sanda* (It became tougher during the pandemic since parents were reliant), not all but mostly especially *ang medyo may edad-edad don* (those who are matured enough). *Reliant sanda sa pagtudlo ka maestra* (They're reliant to teacher's instruction). *Te ang iban indi man kamaan, paano nanda tudluan ang bata nanda nga naga-module kung sanda gani mismo indi gani kakilala ka letra* (Some parents, whose children attend a modular school where even they are unable to distinguish a letter, are unsure of how to teach them)."

Participant 9 also stated, "*Makita mo nga maluya na sa eskwelahan dasun kung kaisa gamay lang gawa nagabuol ka modules* (Sometimes you can see that the school isn't that lively)... ... *ma-experience mo man ang mga modules ka mga bata ibalik nanda kis-a nga daw waay man ti mga answer, gamay lang anda nga ma-answeran te bilang maestra tama gid kabudlay dyang pandemic tulad* (as a teacher, this epidemic is particularly challenging because you will observe that students frequently return modules without answers and can only provide a limited number of responses)."

Participant 11 emphasized, "*Makita mo gid nga ang iban nga mga bata nabudlayan sa pagbasa ka module hay te gabalik lang amg module nga waay ti sabat* (Other learners' inability to read the module is evident by the fact that they simply return it without providing an answer)."

Participant 12 also affirmed, "Para kanakon, nangin isa gid ka challenge ang modality gamit dayang self-learning modules. Daw nangin additional workload lang (The self-learning modules make this modality challenging for me. It appears to be only an added task)."

According to Cruz (2021), these results corroborate a survey done by the civil society organization Movement for Safe, Equitable, Quality, and Relevant Education (SEQuRe), in which it was discovered that public students and teachers claimed that the move to distance learning had left them with heavier workloads, caused internet connectivity and cost issues, and left them with limited resources. According to the poll, 85.2 percent of teachers thought that workloads were increasing. Additionally, the new standard in education places a heavy demand on instructors and students to fulfill every requirement of the program (Aliyyah et al., 2020).

Observing Health Protocols

All instructors, staff, and students are urged to maintain proper hand hygiene and refrain from touching their faces, according to the USM Home (2022) concept. One of the most crucial steps people may take to stop the spread of COVID-19 is frequent hand washing.

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VI (June 2024), p.57-103, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Teachers shared that they are observing health protocols in the highlands especially during the implementation of modular distance learning amid COVID-19 pandemic. With the rising cases, community, especially schools must be complying to the health protocols and maintains them.

To ensure the health and safety of the community, Participant 1 commented on this area and spoke, "*Kami nga teacher kami ang (we, teachers are the) carrier kang (of the) virus, naga-practice man kami gihapon kang (we still practice) health protocol, naga-facemask and then ga-social distancing sa isa kag isa (We wear facemask we practice social distancing form each other). Bale kami lang nagaadto sa kada estudyante (Basically, we are just the one who goes to each learner). Syempre kung magsaka kami na-make sure man nga waay kami kang symptoms mag-adto (Of course if we go to the highlands we make sure we don't have symptoms).*"

Participant 9 also said, "*So gina-explain kananda nga kinahanglan mag-facemask gid mag-adto sa eskwelahan hay ti di man maman-an sa ubos ka maghalin kag sari-sari man nga tawo ang ma-meet nanda. Na-remind man nga manghugas ka alima, kag maninlo man sa palibot eh (We take great care to fully explain to them [parents] why it is important for their children to wear face masks to school because we are from the lowlands and they will be meeting new people. We also tell children to clean their rooms and their surroundings after themselves).*"

The DepEd Order No. 12 provision is supported by these findings. 2020, which states in its principles that it is important to safeguard the health, safety, and well-being of students, teachers, and staff as well as to stop the spread of COVID-19.

Culture Shock

Culture is defined as "the customary belief, social forms, and material traits of racial, religious, or social group; also, the characteristic features of everyday existence (such as the diversions or way of life) shared by people in a place or time" in the Webster's Dictionary of 2002.

It is undeniable that coexisting with native people in isolated locations is frightening. The teacher participants mentioned that they faced culture shock, particularly when they initially were engaged in the IP community, because they had only recently started working in the public school system and some of them had previously attended private schools.

Participant 2 emphasized her experience by saying, "*During my first year teaching at Marandig Primary School, syempre ang expectation ko taas hay waay pa ko kaagi ka saka sa bukid nga amu ka daa muh (of course, I had great expectations because this is my first time seeing the highlands). Ang expectation mo ang makita mo lang sa lowland nga mga fast learners ya mga bata, dasig maka-cope-up (Your expectations align with what you observe in the lowlands, where people learn quickly and adapt to new situations with ease). So pagsaka ko daw medyo na-shock ako ka anda nga sitwasyon (When I come to the highlands, I am quite shocked at their situation). Makita mo nga ang iban dang indi gani kano ka self nanda bala, compare mo diya sa ubos bala tana, mga ano anda itsura, manami... maanyag pero tuya makita mo nga waay iban it mga bayo, waay it mga tsinelas (When compared to students in the lowlands, who have presentable and attractive appearances, you can see that some students there (in the highlands) are unable to even dress themselves up).*"

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Participant 3 also said, "When I was 1st year in teaching I've experienced like a culture shock because I taught before in a private school."

For Participant 4, "As a newly-hired teacher in a public school... uh... there is a big difference in the abilities and skills or unlike in the private school or in the lowland schools."

Participant 5 stressed, "So before the COVID-19 pandemic, teaching in the IP community is quite different from the non-IP school. The differences are observable on the culture and behavior of the learners."

Participant 6 said, "In my first year here *syempre ako ya way ka paghambal ka mga IP sa community daw ka harsh bala* (the way the IP speaks seems like harsh), *biglaanay ya panghambal* (They speak abrasively). Sometimes it hurt me or causes me pain sa akon, *daw nagaka-insulto ka man* (I feel insulted)."

On the other hand, Participant 8 narrated, "So I've experienced this different kind of children. *Sang una gani, may estudyante pa kami nga taas pa kanimo, paano kaw katudlo hay taas pa ang bata kanimo tapos ang age nanda tubo-tubo lang kanimo* (Before, there was a student here who was taller than I am. How then would you instruct the student who is your age and is taller than you)?"

Participant 12 added, "One more thing, in terms of their language, I observed that they have distinct tone when they speak, when you hear them for the first time it seems that you will think they are angry because of the rough approach but actually *hindi man* (not). Also, I sometimes hear unique terms that are maybe part of their culture."

These results support Manz's study from 2003, which he concluded that culture shock is a sudden and upsetting mental or cultural impression brought on by an unwanted event or perception in a foreign culture. It can be depressive, thrilling, or excited in any way. Although the perception of culture shock is unsettling, it does not occur as suddenly as the name shock suggests. In the majority of situations, the true crisis that follows the first euphoria stage is caused by the slow shift from a positive to a negative attitude.

According to Lyons et al. (2006) cited in Giles et al. (2011), the replies of the non-IP teachers are related to the teachers' being young and inexperienced, not speaking the local language, and feeling alone in a bicultural milieu.

Good Relationship with Community of Non-IP Teachers

The best way to enhance teaching and learning in the IP community is to foster positive relationships both within and outside of the classroom.

According to (Santoro, Reid, Crawford, & Simpson, 2021), it's crucial to create informal networks between parents and teachers outside of the school context where relationships of trust can be formed in order to mend the damaged relationship and construct and preserve good school-home partnerships.

Participants who were not IP teachers discussed the positive connections they had to forge upon joining the IP community. People in the community tend to believe that they are safe because of the kind greetings and respect, the generosity displayed by others, the thoughtful acts, and the camaraderie.

Participant 2 talked about how she has a good relationship with the community but admitted that she has difficulty interacting with IP members because she is not one of them. She added, "*Daw nalipay lang ako hay ti daw gin-accept gid ako ka mga tawo tuya* (I'm happy that everyone there genuinely accepted me). *Maman-an mo gid nga na-love nanda ikaw kag na-accept nanda ikaw hay ti simple lang, padar-an da pa ikaw ka bugas,*

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Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VI (June 2024), p.57-103, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

padar-an da pa ikaw ka mga turulanhon (By virtue of their provision of veggies and rice, you will know that they liked and accepted you)."

Participant 5 also said, "So I am absolutely thankful that the indigenous community are very supportive on the new system of education... In terms *duman tana sa mga parents dya man da sanda naga-bulig man kanamon syempre dya kami naga-stay katong may face-to-face weekly ang tinir namon* (We reside here once a week when there is face-to-face, so the parents are here to assist us). So, *kung kaisa manami ang mga ginikanan diya sa bukid hay ginataw-an da kami ka mga fruits, vegetables nga para sa amon nga pagkaon man* (Sometimes the parents are nice because they give us fruits and vegetables as our food). *Kung kaisa ginabalikan namon daa ka gamay lang nga kwarta para man sa anda nga pang-allowance man* (We occasionally return them a small sum as an allowance)."

According to Participant 6, "So the first challenge nga naano ko di is how to handle people hay syempre lain-lain andang background, their way of living.

Ang isa lang ka nanamian ko diya sa IP community, mataas gid ang pagturok kag pagrespeto nanda sa mga teachers (One thing I like here in the Ip community, they respect and look up to teachers). *Bisan nagareklamo man sanda* (Eventhough they complain) at the end *ginasunod gid nanda ang teachers kay gina-honor gid nanda ang mga words ka teachers* (they really honor and follow the words of the teachers)."

Participant 8 asserted, "So *ang challenge gid kanakon* is (the most challenging on me) how would you adapt in the indigenous community *kay te kami stay-in kami* (because we stay here). For one whole week *dyan ka sa eskwelahan tapos ma-adapt ka sa culture ka community nga waay mo pa nakilal-an bala* (you stay there at school then you will adapt to the community's culture that you don't even know). So *ang gin-ubra namon* (what we are doing) ... *uh... ga-reach out kami sa community* (we reach out to the community), *gakipag-estorya kami sa ginikanan syempre para man-an mo background ka imu estudyante* (we communicate to parents so that we will know our learner's background). *Asta naka-cope up kami, naka-adapt kami ka anda pagginawi diya sa takas* (here in the Highlands, we adopted their way of life until we were able to adjust).

I'm very happy man *hay te ang mga tawo diya sa takas indi man sanda ti* (the people here are not) hostile towards *sa iban* (others)."

Participant 9 affirmed, "Eventhough *nga indi man ako it* (that I am not an) IP *nga na-assign diya sa* (that was assigned here at) Supanga ES, *daw okay man sanda ang mga tawo ang pag-treat nanda kanakon hay ti kon mayad kaw mayad man ang pag-treat nanda kanimo* (they are considerate in the manner they treat me because they reciprocate kindness)."

Participant 11 added, "As a non-IP teacher, *ginakabig man nanda ako bilang daw* (they treat me like an) IP *man (also) kag indi man ti liwan nga tawo sa anda nga lugar* (not just like somebody in their community). *Manami man sanda hay ginatatap ka man nanda it mayad tapos kis-a may ginapadara mga malido, mga kagang, banag*. (They treat you well and occasionally give you "malido," "freshwater crabs," or "banag," which is nice)."

Participant 12 emphasized, "In terms of my relation to the community, I made a big adjustment, since I am not an IP. I have to understand first their way of living, their situation, and especially their culture. The people in the IP community are kind towards me. *Bisan sang first time ko nga na-assign sa takas* (Even it's my first time to be assigned on the highlands), they accepted me as part of their community also because for them they value, respect and look-up teachers. They are also supportive in our schools' activities and programs."

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These results back up a study by Javilla and Fabilla (2019) who said that as time passes, teachers get ingrained in the community as a result of the kindness and gratitude shown to them for their service.

Additionally, the claim of Ball (2014) stressed that relationships and communication are key to working and living in a remote indigenous community. The fact that teachers are welcomed and respected in the indigenous society demonstrates an impressive sign of the people's willingness to receive training and their eagerness to learn.

Adjustment of Married Teachers

To adjust is to successfully and cheerfully integrate into society. According to the expectations of the society in which he or she lives, every member of the society must adjust. Only in society can an individual find fulfillment for their desires. The society is the one who helps them. Adjustment makes life more satisfying. Every stage of life has its own unique value for adjustment (Meenakshi, 2017).

Married teacher-participants imparted testimonies of the adjustments they had to make when living in the IP community and tensions they experienced leaving home.

Participant 5 stated her adjustment as a married teacher saying, "For me, *sang una pa nga bag-o ako diya Ma'am syempre may baby don ako* (before when I am still a newbie here, I already had a baby), so, *mabudlay para kanakon hay gamay pa ya bata ko* (it's hard for me)so, *kung kaisa gusto mo man daad nga mag-uli hay kung kaisa nagasakit man ya ulo ka bata mo* (as much as I would like to, I can't go home, even though my child is not feeling well), *pero hay ti teacher kita Ma'am so dang kinahanglan ma-focus man kita di sa aton nga ubra so biskan nabudlayan ako, gina-balance ko lang* (however, we are teacher so we need to focus in our work, I just balance). *May ginabinlan lang ako nga tana lang maalaga ka bata ko para maka-focus man ako di sa akon nga ubra* (I just have someone to look after my child so that I can focus here on my work)."

According to Participant 8, "At first *mabudlay gid eh* (it's really hard), especially *kanakon nga* (on my part that) I have two kids. *Te mabudlay kay one whole week indi mo ma-monitor imu kabataan* (it's hard because one whole week, you can't monitor your kids)... *syempre ang imu nga focus tao mo dulang sa mga kabataan* (of course you have to redirect your focus to your learners) on how you adjust yourself *dulang nga ang imu emotions indi mo ma-mix sa imu nga ubra* (so, that your emotion won't affect your work).

Amu daa ya mga adjustments nga dapat himuon ka mga married teachers (These are the adjustments that we have to make as married teachers)."

Participant 9 stressed, "It's a big challenge *hay te pamilyado* (that I have a family), *may mga nabilin ka to sa ubos pira kaw ka days diya* (you leave them at the lowlands and you're here for days), Monday to Friday, *mabudlay kag masubo man daad eh hay marayo ka sa imu family kapin pa hay may mga gagmay nga mga kabataan nga gaereskwela man* (being separated from your family is difficult and depressing, especially considering I have young children who attend school). So, *i-balance mo lang ng imu kaugalingon kag isip nga kinahanglan dedikado ka man sa imu obligasyon* (You must maintain a healthy balance between your body and mind in order to be committed to your obligations). *Kung kaisa te hay indi man ti manami ya signal, ngita-ngita lang ka mayad-mayad nga signal para maka-communicate sa mga kabataan kag sa pamilya sa ubos kon may time* (Since the signal is

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Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

poor, if you have time, just try to look for place where there is signal so you can talk to your relatives and children who live in the lowlands)."

For Participant 12, "Before when I was assigned in an IP community, I am still single. So it was quite fine; however, I still have my family left in the lowland everyday. And now this pandemic, I am in adjusting stage since I am now married and I have a 10-month-old daughter. It is difficult for me and for my husband to give time to our family, given that my husband's nature of work is also not easy. So, it's a more on time management and open-mindedness *lang* (only) for us to cope with work or family matters."

These results back up the research by Rizvi (2016) revealed that teachers' marital status had little bearing on how well they were adjusting to their careers. It does not appear to conflict with teachers' professional obligations or institutional allegiance. Consequently, it has no discernible effect on the professional adjustment.

Giving Extrinsic Motivation

Motivation from without is not a negative thing. In order to keep people motivated and focused on their goals, external rewards can be a beneficial and successful strategy. This can be especially crucial when individuals are required to finish a task that they find challenging or boring, such as a tiresome project at work (Cherry, 2021). It has been observed by the teacher-participants that the feeding program enhances the attendance of the IP learners. Furthermore, teachers were seeking ways and exerting efforts to provide some reinforcements for the learners to be active in school.

According to Participant 1, "*Syempre may ara kami nga nahatag* (Of course we have something to give) every week *sa ila* (for them) as a reinforcement or *ginahatag kada saka namon nga* (everytime we come to the highlands) something *nga daw may i-give kananda para at least ma-boost man anda self nga mag-eskwela sanda* (that might boost them to come to school), just like *mga pagkaon or mga biscuits or mga dulsi dyan or mga gamit sa pag-eskwela* (food, biscuits, or candies, or anything that can be used for schooling), at least *ma-boost anda self... kon may dara kami is present daa sanda*(they would be encouraged to be present in school, if we have something for them)."

Participant 9 also highlighted, "*Tulad waay don kami naga-feeding sa mga bata* (Now, we don't have the feeding for learners), *ginataw-an dulang namon ka mga tinapay* (we just give them buns) or milk so *makit-an mo man nga kung kaisa 100% sanda kung may itao halin sa DepEd* (If you occasionally give them something from DepEd, you'll be able to see that they're 100% present) *hay ti bisan amu lang da tana daw big deal don da tana nga* (because whatever it is, it's already a big deal as) one way of motivation *nga taw-an sanda ka benefits sa eskwelahan kag madasig sanda maabtik sanda* (they have benefits from the school, so they became active and motivated)."

These results back with the study by Dickson (2018), which came to the conclusion that using extrinsic motivation throughout the teaching process encourages students to achieve greater academic levels in social studies.

Complex Work Arrangement During Pandemic

During the term of the COVID-19 pandemic's state of national emergency, government organizations like the DepEd may implement one or more of the alternative work arrangements that the CSC has identified. These include work-from-home options, skeleton staffing, reduced workweeks of four days, staggered work hours, and other unconventional work arrangements. appropriate or applicable to the organization subject to

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the ongoing community quarantine given the employees' line of work (DepEd Order No. O11, s. 2020).

Teachers affirmed that they experienced complex work arrangement during pandemic stating that sometimes they were not able to facilitate well the distribution and retrieval of modules, they cannot accommodate the parents' queries and concerns, and they find it difficult to reproduce modules in their schools due to the unavailability of electricity.

Participant 2 commented on the complex work arrangement during the pandemic saying, "Very challenging *gid tana Ma'am hay isipon mo lang* (because just imagine) Work-from-home so *kinahanglan lang namon magpadara ka* (you need to send) modules, *ipadara lang sa motor* (you just ask someone who drives motorcycle), *ipadara sa eskwelahan namon kag sanda dulang tuya mag-facilitate* (you'll just send it to school and let them facilitate the distribution)."

According to Participant 3, "As a teacher *gusto mo man daad magbalik sa imu school adlaw-adlaw* (we really wanted to go back to school everyday). Atleast ya (the) parents *mag-adto dayan mamangkot kanimu, may pamangkutan siya 'Sir paano dang amu ka dya?'* (yhey'll have someone to ask if they come). But there's memorandum of DedEd nga like 50% or 80% *lang ya ma-duty* (will report to duty), then *may* (there's) skeletal nga *ginatawag* (that's so called) so *dang daw indi mo gid matao ya best mo nga magbalik adlaw-adlaw* (you cannot put orth yout utmost to report everyday)."

For Participant 10, "Sa (In) production ka amon nga (of our) modules, *naga-skelatal arrangement kami* (we are in skeletal arrangement), *ang half naga-duty sa school ang half naga-print ka modules diya sa banwa* (half of us reports to school and half of us prints modules in the lowland). So *indi pwede nga magtingob kami ka-saka hay since waay kami to kuryente* (Since we lack electricity, it is not possible for us to all report)."

These results confirm a research by Sharafizad et al. (2011) that found that simply giving flexible work schedules would not guarantee employee acceptance. Furthermore, the results suggest that academic and non-academic workers use flexible work arrangements in quite different ways.

Exhaustion

Exhaustion is one of the three dimensions of burnout (World Health Organization, 2019).

When a teacher feels too worn out to work any longer, they have experienced burnout. Teachers-participants declared they are feeling worn out when teaching in the IP community before and during the epidemic as a result of long commutes and the reproduction of modules. Participant 2, "Sa Monday nga ran hay the *ma-travel kami sa motor 1 hour and 30 mins pa abi dayon ma-walk pa kami 3-4 hours sa amon nga school* (during Monday we have to travel 1 hour and 30 mins riding the motorcycle and then we will walk for 3-4 hours going to our school). So *ang Monday nga day-a kumbaga pag-abot namon ipahuway dulang namon hay ti kapoy don kami kapanaw ti and one day nga da daw uyang don* (in other words, since we are already tired from travelling, we merely need to rest on Monday when we arrive, making that day feel like a waste of time)."

Participant 9 "Magtravel paadto sa Supanga, *tama ka kapoy kag risgo man gid eh* (travelling going to Supanga, is very exhausting and also risky)."

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VI (June 2024), p.57-103, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Participant 12, "On my part as a teacher, *ang* experience *magtudlo dukaron nga* (my experience teaching this) pandemic *mahambal ko nga makapoy gid* (is really exhausting). *Kada semana, mahingagaw gid ka reproduce ka modules* (Every week, you have to cope in the reproduction of modules)."

These findings support the 2017 Skills and Employability Survey (SES) cited by White (2019) wherein it shows that teaching is exhausting and more likely to be classed as 'high strain' profession.

Support from Stakeholders

It is emphasized how crucial it is for students, parents, the community, and administrators to actively participate in the design and implementation of the many school operations. Because modular distance learning is a shared duty, collaboration is crucial (Keim and Olguin, 2009).

Teachers recognized stakeholders' support and involvement during the pandemic particularly on their benevolent assistance in helping the learners' in answering modules.

Participant 1 acknowledged on the support they receive about it stating, "*Nagapasalamat kami* (we are thankful) it's because *nga* last year so *may ara pa nga iban nga mga* (there were) stakeholders like Philippine Army *nga nagbulig sa ila para tudluan ang amon estudyante* (who helped in teaching our learners). *Kumbaga sanda don nag-assist sa paghatag namon module* (They thereby helped spread our modules, in other words)."

Furthermore, Participant 9 added, "*Kaisa batian namon, may mga army nga naturutudluan sanda te kis-a ma-check mo man mga modules nanda may mga answers man* (When we check their modules, there may be answers because we've occasionally heard that the army is teaching them)."

These findings support the study conducted by Cejalvo (2021) which shows that professional support is one of the supports extended by the external stakeholders. Professional support included sponsoring a resolution for modular distance learning, facilitating designated areas of the barangay for the distribution and retrieval of modules, and monitoring.

Proposed Policy Recommendation

The DepEd has an existing policy on indigenous peoples' education but no specific policy for teachers who are teaching in the indigenous people community.

Based on the results of the study, the following are the proposed policy for recommendation to provide assistance and cater the concerns and needs of teachers who are teaching in the IP community:

Design Policy for Non-IP teachers

It is recommended to design specific policy for non-IP teachers who are designated to IP schools so that there would be corresponding legal basis for teachers in terms of addressing their rights, protection, and benefits.

Strengthen Localization

It is recommended that the employment and assignment of teachers should be more locally focused, with priority given to lawful inhabitants of the barrio, municipality, city, or province where the school is located. Specifically, teachers who enter the service with specialized IP items must remain in the IP schools where they are designated so that they can steadfastly serve their community.

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Design Exclusive Work Arrangement

Due to the travel of teachers, their academic teaching loads are affected. Hence, it is recommended that work should be arranged to complete the required number of hours in a day. Ancillary activities and programs of the district that require participation and expectations should not be mandatory on the part of the teachers who are teaching in the IP community schools located in far flung barangays and hard to reach areas.

Increase Hardship and Allowance

Increase Hardship Allowance to additional 5% of the annual basic salary of teachers (multi-grade teachers and TICs) in the IP community especially those who are assigned to areas characterized as extraordinarily hard, uncomfortable and extremely difficult and are exposed to hazard due to the nature and/or location of their work.

Additional Fund Allocation to MOOE

Particularly for schools located in the IP community, the Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) spent on activities and necessities that support learning programs and help in maintaining a safe and healthy environment in schools are insufficient. According to World Bank (2016), MOOE is the only operational funding the schools received. The school heads or TICs could not put as much items within the given budget. Although the schools spend more frequently on office supplies, materials needed for repair and maintenance higher percentage of the MOOE is utilized in hauling and transportation. Hence, MOOE alone is not enough to cover up all the expenditures of the schools.

Provision of Free Transportation Service

It is recommended that they should provide free transport service to teachers assigned in far-flung IP community through the courtesy of the Local Government Unit. It is pertinent to mention that the government do not provide weekly or daily free transportation facility to teachers going to the IP community where they are stationed.

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Chapter 5

Summary, Insights, and Recommendations

This chapter presents the summary of the study, the insights drawn from the findings, and the recommendations arrived at by the researcher.

Summary

The main purpose of the study was to determine the teachers' experiences living in the indigenous people community before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the Schools District of Calinog II for school year 2021-2022.

The study used descriptive method using in-depth interview.

The study employed qualitative research design using ethnography.

The participants of the study were the twelve (12) purposively chosen teachers of public elementary school in the Schools District of Calinog II who are teaching in the IP schools.

The research instrument utilized in the study was a researcher-made interview schedule. A panel of experts validated the instrument. Comments and suggestions were considered.

Audio and video recorders were also used for data gathering and documentation depending upon the permission of the participants.

Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data gathered.

Findings

The following were the findings of the study:

Most of the teacher participants are young adults and female. All of them are Teachers I. Most of them had a short length of service. Most of them are single. Seven of them are non-IPs, and five are IPs.

Based on the results of the interview conducted to the participants, the experience of teachers living in the IP community were classified as difficulty in workplace, safety and security, learners' habitual behavior, DDU (depressed, dilapidated, & underserved) school, far from the town and difficult roads, teaching the basic literacy, poor learners' achievement, learning modality as a challenge, observing health protocols, culture shock, good communication with the community of non-IP teachers, adjustment of married teachers, giving extrinsic motivation, complex work arrangement during pandemic, exhaustion, and support from external stakeholders.

A proposed policy recommendation was made based on the results of the study to provide assistance and cater the concerns, gaps encountered, and needs of teachers who are teaching in the IP community. These are to Design Policy for Non-IP teachers, Strengthen Localization, Design Exclusive Work Arrangement, Increase of Hardship Allowance, Additional Fund Allocation to MOOE, Provision of Free Transportation Service.

Insights

Based on the findings, the following insights were drawn:

In contrast to traditional training, IP education frequently employs methods that are unique to it. It is acknowledged and included how crucial it is to emphasize indigenous

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knowledge, abilities, practices, and values. It is essential to comprehend how IP learners see the world in order to instruct them successfully. Learning is only meaningful and valuable for the rest of their life when links are created between the new material being presented and their known way of living. All efforts must respect their identity as IPs, even while educational changes are meant to benefit their community.

Considerations should be given because non-IP teachers are geographically a little behind the IP communities' cultures. Newly-hired teachers are commonly assigned to difficult responsibilities or far-off schools that are part of IP communities. Specifically those who are non-IP, single, and female predominate, frequently struggle with culture shock, adaptation, and adjustment.

Technology creates more parity. Teachers and students from indigenous communities are given the chance to have a better future through the use of these. Analyzing the method by which technology is introduced in these communities is essential for the evaluation of the influence of technology on the empowerment of indigenous populations to be successful. In this aspect, external actors like donors or government representatives can be extremely helpful in assisting the local community in appropriating the technologies to fit their own local and cultural demands.

To create an environment where teachers and students can learn from one another, openness is required. Respect for the culture that defines the entire community reflects respect for the dignity of each individual. When education programs for these populations are encouraged rather than mandated, they are most effective. As education lays an emphasis on the various features that have always been a part of it, each of the participants must be aware of the community's wealth in both natural and human resources.

Rural roads are essential for assisting society's most vulnerable citizens. IP schools are frequently found in remote barangays or difficult-to-reach locations, where teachers must deal with things like challenging roads, underprivileged communities, and less-prioritized schools. To ensure the safety of both the teachers and the students, it is necessary that the road remain well-compacted.

The new learning modality, specifically the Printed Modular Distance Learning, showed the DepEd's enthusiasm and commitment to continue delivering education amidst COVID-19. Despite the pandemic crisis, they still found alternative ways to augment the gaps and needs they encounter.

Teachers become resilient when their learners do. No matter how bad one's circumstances are in life, education is still important. It is valued highly in this nation as a way to improve one's quality of life. This has never been truer than during the COVID-19 outbreak that hit the nation. Despite the financial and physical hardships the pandemic caused, learners kept up their studies.

Innovation is the way to go. The need of considering educational innovations must be emphasized by schools as they make the gradual adjustment to the new normal and work to recover from the destructive impacts of the pandemic. One problem is that MOOE resources for schools were insufficient to cover all of the demands of modular distance learning, especially in remote indigenous communities where financing is scarce. It is best to be ready, even if it is unlikely that another pandemic of the magnitude of the COVID-19 pandemic will ever affect the entire world. Schools especially in IP communities may do this by encouraging a creative mentality and going above and beyond to support both teachers and learners.

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Parental participation in the IP community in educating their children is a meaningful involvement. Parents are essential in helping their kids achieve better in school and maintain decent manners. Parental involvement in their children's education is a significant role for Indigenous People (IP) that directly promotes student learning.

Relationship between the academic community and stakeholders can be strengthened through actions that would cultivate healthy relationships in order to strengthen cooperation is necessary for the realization of the "new normal" method of imparting instruction process.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following points are given for future considerations:

The results provided contextual pieces of evidence about the multifaceted experiences that confront teachers in the IP community before and amid the current pandemic crisis. Teachers are recommended to engage in making innovation and simple classroom action researches to remediate existing problems, to address concerns in teaching in the difficult areas, and to further improve the quality of learning even in different learning modality.

To satisfy the demands of the teaching and learning process during the pandemic in the community of indigenous people, teachers should develop appropriate plans and put those plans into practice. They ought to approach the problem with a growth mindset, accept changes, and explore possibilities by stepping outside of their comfort zones. It is recommended that symposia may be conducted to parents and to community regarding topics on responsible parenthood, patriotism, health practices/protocols and other matters related to the community's current situation.

The school heads may work together with the teachers to deal with their experiences. They may engage in discussions, orientations, and meetings may be held beforehand which aim to prepare teachers who are new in service especially the non-IP teachers who will be deployed in the IP community.

Mental health awareness activities may be implemented in schools to serve as a support system for teachers, in order or them to have more positive energy for themselves, their learners, and their family.

Since Non-IP teachers have difficulty understanding new methods and concepts due to their lack of expertise and experience in the field in which they must teach, the district or division may offer effective professional development programs that will contain concepts.

In order to solve the difficulties teachers in the community of indigenous peoples have as they transition to the new normal teaching practices, higher offices and school authorities may collaborate with those educators. To successfully give high-quality instruction, teachers should have access to the necessary materials and trainings.

District offices may be allowed by the DepEd to offer contextualized in-service programs that are concentrated on individualized issues. These initiatives could focus on new curriculum conferences, classroom management strategies, or topic matters.

The Department of Education and the SDO may produce contextualized modules that are comprehensive to lighten the teachers' burden so that teachers will have focus on teaching-related activities.

These experiences are advised to be taken into account as inputs for the improvement of the current educational system. Since there is an undergoing major

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restructuring of the curriculum, policymakers in the field of education and curriculum planners should fill the huge gap between what is written and what is implemented. They should plan a curriculum wherein competencies are attainable to develop in schools especially in times of crisis especially in the IP communities.

Further research could be conducted on the awareness of the need to look at approaches and perceptions of school heads concerning the performance or competence of teachers who teach in the IP community.

A similar research study may be conducted but may consider other variables not used in this study.

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Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

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World Education Connect

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VI (June 2024), p.57-103, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.12199176

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